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Evaluation of novel agroforestry-based apple production systems

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Executive Summary

Novel land use systems that integrate woody species into the agricultural landscape have the potential to balance productivity with protection of the environment and the maintenance of ecosystem services. Although the potential of agroforestry-based agricultural systems has been demonstrated in principle, information of usefulness in the context of European low-input production systems is lacking. Integrating top fruit production into an agroforestry system, where woody species are integrated with crop production, may have a beneficial effect on the control of plant pathogens such as scab (*Venturia inaequalis*). However, the introduction of such systems into European high-yielding traditional apple production systems will meet substantial obstacles as the approach affects not only agronomic performance but also well-established fruit production traditions. This research aimed to evaluate an apple/arable agroforestry approach as a sustainable strategy for reducing copper inputs in organic and low input systems using two case studies; Wakelyns Agroforestry, Suffolk, UK (Section 2) and Whitehall Farm, Cambridgeshire, UK (Section 3).

Research focused on five elements that are likely to be impacted by an agroforestry systems approach to no-copper use:

- (i) Yield and quality of apples (Sections 2 and 3)
- (ii) Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases (Sections 2 and 3),
- (iii) Impact on ecosystem services and functionality (Sections 2 and 3),
- (iv) The economics of agroforestry-based apple production (Section 4),
- (v) Impact on management activities (Section 5).

The Case Studies

Wakelyns Agroforestry, an organic silvoarable research site, was established in 1994 on 22.5 ha in eastern England. Within the 2ha apple/arable agroforestry system a diverse mix of 21 varieties of apple trees on MM111 rootstock are interspersed with 7 timber species, in north/south rows with 12 m-wide crop alleys between adjacent rows. Cereals, potatoes, field vegetables and fertility-building leys are grown in rotation within the alleys. The apple trees cover 2.5% of the land area in the 2ha system. A local modern 0.6 ha organic orchard acted as a benchmark for comparison. Research at Wakelyns was carried out in 2012 and 2013.

The agroforestry system at Whitehall Farm is much more commercial than that at Wakelyns Agroforestry in Case Study 1, in terms of design and scale. Whitehall Farm is 100ha organic arable farm on high quality soil near Peterborough, in eastern England. Previously managed as an intensive arable system, the eastern half of the farm entered into organic conversion in 2007, while the rest entered conversion in August 2009. In October 2009, 4,500 apple trees, consisting of 13 varieties were planted in rows running NE/SW 27m apart, with 3m spacing of trees within rows. The understory was sown before tree planting with a 3m band of nectar flower mixtures and legumes. The 24m remaining between rows is cropped on an organic rotation including cereals, vegetables and legume fertility-building leys. Late maturing apple varieties have been chosen to allow harvesting of the alley crops first. Three apple varieties were chosen for inclusion in the research, based on number of replicated rows available and their degree of scab resistance, to include the

susceptible variety Bramley, the moderately resistant variety Falstaff and the resistant variety Red Windsor. There was no local commercial organic orchard to use as a benchmark and so Willock Farm, a local heritage orchard, was used as a comparison. Research at Whitehall Farm was carried out in 2014 and 2015.

Yield and quality of apples

At Wakelyns Agroforestry, apple yields in 2012 were adversely affected by the weather, with low fruit set due to late frosts and heavy rain. Despite this, the yield from the agroforestry system was comparable with standard figures when scaled up from 2.5% land area under apple production to 100% apples, and even at just 2.5% cover, appeared to out-perform a local organic orchard used for comparison. In 2013, the yields were higher in both systems (2.24 t/ha from the orchard and 0.72 t/ha from the agroforestry), and again, when scaled up to 100% land cover, the agroforestry apple yields compared well with standard figures (Class I & II: 19.25 t/ha from the agroforestry vs. 14 t/ha from orchards at peak production).

At Whitehall Farm, tree rows account for 10% land area with 85 trees/ha; scaling up to 100% apples, yields in 2014 ranged from 0.25 t/ha to 5.95 t/ha and in 2015 from 1.36 t/ha to 15.18 t/ha, which compares with standard yields for 5 year old orchard of 3 t/ha and an organic orchard in peak production (6-11 years) of 14 t/ha. There was a wide range of yields from different varieties and in the two years, with two of the low yielding varieties (Falstaff, Bramley) in the same field, which may indicate problems with pollination or mineral deficiency although these two varieties also had high levels of scab in 2014. Considering that the apple trees at Whitehall were planted only in 2009 and so the system is still establishing and developing, the apple yields look promising, with some varieties performing much better than others.

Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases

Neither case study systems spray to control for scab or other diseases or pests; scab was detected in both systems during the years of study. At Wakelyns, scab levels were several times lower than in the nearby organic orchard in both 2012 and 2013. Although no firm general conclusion can be drawn from this case study, it appears as if there may be indications of a potential positive impact on reducing scab levels within the agroforestry. This could be due to the very low densities of apple trees. Also, that while some varieties may fail to set fruit or have high levels of scab, the high diversity of apple varieties within the agroforestry means that other varieties will have compensate and so buffer against extreme losses of yields. However, further research will be required to confirm this theory.

Scab was recorded in the apples at Whitehall Farm at quite high levels, particularly in 2014, and in one variety (Falstaff) in 2015, although the resistant variety Red Windsor maintained its resistance. However, the apple varieties studied seemed to perform poorly, while other varieties in the system yielded well and had fewer pests and diseases, which demonstrated the value of planting a wide range of varieties. The varieties were planted in blocks, which is likely to have facilitated the spread of pests and diseases, despite the crop alleys in between tree rows. It may therefore be better to mix varieties within the rows and fields, although this then becomes a challenge to manage and harvest efficiently.

At Wakelyns, the impacts of secondary pests and diseases varied between the agroforestry system and the orchard, with higher levels of sawfly, aphid, capsid and moth damage in the agroforestry apples. Codling moth damage was higher in the pre-harvest orchard apples.

At Whitehall Farm, a range of secondary pests and diseases were recorded in the agroforestry and orchard systems in 2014 and 2015. In 2014, moth damage was common in the Bramley and Falstaff apples, as was open flesh wounds caused by insects and/or birds, while Red Windsor suffered high levels of capsid damage. This may reflect the potential conflict in sowing wildflower mixtures under trees to encourage pollinators into the open arable landscape but causing an increase in capsid damage as a result of the flowering plants encouraging higher populations of capsids. In 2015, sawfly damage was the main problem in the developing fruit, despite the removal of infected fruit in the agroforestry systems in June 2015, with highest levels in the Willock and Falstaff small apples. In the large fruit, Bramley apples suffered from higher levels of moth and earwig damage.

The results from Wakelyns and Whitehall Farm confirm previous research on agroforestry systems that while some pests are reduced in agroforestry systems, other pest groups may be observed in higher numbers, and shifts in relative importance of pest groups may present novel management problems and influence crop choice.

Impact on ecosystem services and functionality

Three ecosystem services were investigated: biodiversity of beneficial arthropods; regulation of the microclimate; and soil health. The biodiversity impacts of the agroforestry systems were mixed; at Wakelyns Agroforestry, predatory and parasitic wasps were recorded in higher numbers, and *Lassioglossum* and *Bombus* bees in lower numbers, compared with the control orchard, perhaps reflecting differences in levels of disturbance from management and understory vegetation, with fewer floral resources in the agroforestry.

It was expected that wind speeds would be higher in the agroforestry compared with the orchard due to the lower density of trees, and the alley design. However, there was no consistent pattern of lower wind speeds in the orchard; the system at Wakelyns is protected to the south by a row of tall poplar trees and this may reduce wind speeds in the agroforestry. Soil temperature was significantly higher in the summer and lower in the winter in the crop alleys, demonstrating the buffering effect of trees on temperature extremes.

Variation in soil types between the case study systems and their controls makes it difficult to draw any firm conclusions regarding the effects of agroforestry on soil quality. However, it is interesting to note that soil organic matter is lower in the orchard compared with both the tree row and crop alley at Wakelyns, even though the alley is regularly cultivated and cropped. There were no differences between the agroforestry and orchard with regards soil respiration rates, but within the agroforestry system, respiration rates in the tree row were higher than in the alley, perhaps reflecting the more stable nature of the soils under the trees.

The economics of agroforestry-based apple production

An inevitable question about any farming system is whether it is profitable and therefore able to contribute to the farm's economic survival. The pattern of cash-flows can also be important: for some farmers a large initial capital investment may not be possible even if later returns would make such an investment highly desirable. Economic studies of agroforestry systems have shown that

financial benefits are a consequence of increasing the diversity and productivity of the systems, influenced by market and price fluctuations of timber, livestock and crops. However, studies of systems combining arable and apple production have not been carried out so far. Two approaches were used to examine economic performance of agroforestry-based apple production, using data from Case Study 2: a simple Net Present Value (NPV); and FarmSAFE (a model specifically developed to determine and compare the profitability of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems at a farm and a landscape-scale, which is also based on the NPV approach).

The calculation using the simple NPV calculator yielded a positive NPV, thus it can be seen that the agroforestry system is profitable. The spreadsheet also highlights the reliance on subsidies and agri-environmental payments. In 2014 the income from the single farm payment and HLS is 66% of the total margin. The NPV calculation can also be used to investigate the impact if the agroforestry system was replaced with a fully arable (all wheat) system or with a system that only produced apples. If it was still eligible for the HLS payment then the wheat-only system would be more profitable than the agroforestry system. In the case that the site is not eligible for any agri-environment payments the NPV would reduce to give a substantial reduction in income. It is likely that the income would lie somewhere between these two extremes. In such a case it is likely that it would be less profitable than the agroforestry but closer in value to it. The NPV calculation can also be used to investigate the impact if the agroforestry system was converted to an apple orchard. This suggests that the apple-only system would be loss-making. It is possible that the apple-only system could be made profitable but it appears that it is unlikely that it would be as profitable as the agroforestry system without major changes to the operation.

The FarmSAFE model also shows that in the total absence of grants, arable production is more profitable than the agroforestry. This highlights the fact that the agroforestry is more profitable due to the HLS environmental payments on the tree strip. However the model also shows that in its current form (i.e. with the HLS payment), the agroforestry system is preferable to the arable. Similarly to the simple NPV calculation results, a scaled-up version of the tree-component of the agroforestry results in an orchard system which is loss-making. However, it was possible using FarmSAFE to calculate break-even apple yields and apple prices which would give zero NPV. These break-even values were within plausible values (especially for the prices) and it is likely that a combination of improved prices and improved yields could combine to give a positive NPV.

It is worth emphasising that these results are for one agroforestry system in a particular part of the UK which was planted for a very specific purpose. The results suggest that the agroforestry system is the most profitable approach as long as it remains eligible for HLS or similar grants. However, it was planted mainly with the aim of reducing soil erosion rather than with profitability as its main aim. It was noticeable when checking the break-even prices and yields for the scaled-up apple orchard system that the yields and prices currently obtained within the agroforestry system are relatively low. This may be due to the location of the farm (it is not in an apple-growing area of the UK) which may not provide optimum growing conditions or due to other factors that are specific to the farm. It is therefore difficult to treat these results as representative of UK agroforestry as a whole and care must be taken in interpreting them. However, for this specific farm they suggest that the agroforestry system is profitable and, with the inclusion of an HLS grant, is more profitable than an arable system with no HLS grant. The results also suggest that if the farmer wanted to move over to

a fully orchard system then a number of changes would be needed to obtain higher yields and prices as a simple scaling-up of the agroforestry system would not be profitable.

Impact on management activities

This research aimed to identify the main management implications of novel agroforestry-based apple production systems by interviewing both primary and secondary adopters from four case study systems within England. Content analysis was used to identify dominant topics and concepts, coding the interviews thematically, the development of thick descriptions for each topic to explore the context and meaning of each issue, cross-case comparisons to highlight patterns across interviews, grouping codes into meaningful categories and exploring the relationships between these categories.

This study provided useful insight into the potential benefits and management challenges associated with novel silvoarable apple systems. Although farmers reported a number of management issues and unforeseen challenges in the design, establishment and on-going operation of their systems, they also spoke of substantial benefits in terms of product diversification, increased biodiversity, reduced soil erosion, and the provision of shelter, with most believing that their systems had been successful in meeting their objectives, suggesting such benefits may well outweigh any management inconveniences. Nevertheless, a number of approaches to mitigating the management impacts of integrating apple and cereal production were identified. These included appropriate system design, de-synchronization of management activities, effective management of tree-crop competition and weeds, and the ability of farmers and contractors to adapt management practices.

Evidence of farmer-led adoption suggests farmers perceive silvoarable apple systems to be viable, implying scope for wider uptake within England. However this study also identified a number of substantial knowledge gaps. This calls for not only further documentation of existing systems but further trials on their establishment, operation and commercial performance. As recognized by all five of the farmers interviewed, in addition to continued research, favourable policy changes and conversion grants will be required for wider adoption of agroforestry-based apple production within the UK.

Conclusions

The two case study systems provided contrasting approaches to agroforestry-based apple production in terms of scale and design. The low density, high diversity approach at Wakelyns Agroforestry seemed to have benefits in terms of reducing disease levels, and could work well in a diverse, potentially small-scale system such as a market garden, where apples could contribute to direct marketing channels such as vegetable box schemes or farm shops. The commercial silvoarable system at Whitehall Farm showed that an agroforestry approach *per se* is not successful at reducing scab levels. However, if combined with careful selection of resistant varieties and, if possible, mixed planting of varieties, the other benefits that agroforestry brings, particularly to arable systems, may make this approach attractive to arable farmers looking to diversify their enterprises or protect their farms against environmental problems.

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1. Introduction

Novel land use systems that integrate woody species into the agricultural landscape have the potential to balance productivity with protection of the environment and the maintenance of ecosystem services (Jose, 2009). An emphasis on managing rather than reducing complexity promotes a functionally biodiverse system with both ecological and economic interactions between trees and crops and livestock (Lundgren, 1982). Although the potential of agroforestry-based agricultural systems has been demonstrated in principle (Quinkenstein et al, 2009), information of usefulness in the context of European low-input production systems is lacking. Also, the introduction of such systems into European high-yielding traditional apple production systems will meet substantial obstacles as the approach affects not only agronomic performance but also well-established fruit production traditions. As part of the European FP7-funded project 'Innovative strategies for copper-free low-input and organic farming systems (CO-FREE, www.co-free.eu)', we have been evaluating an innovative apple/arable agroforestry system as a potentially sustainable strategy for reducing copper inputs in organic and low input systems. The aim is to provide information on the potential of agroforestry in the European context.

Integrating top fruit production into an agroforestry system, where woody species are integrated with crop production, may have a beneficial effect on the control of plant pathogens such as scab (*Venturia inaequalis*) due to a number of mechanisms:

- A greater distance between tree rows in agroforestry systems, with crops in the adjoining alleys, is likely to reduce the spread of pathogens. This has been recorded for crop pathogens in agroforestry systems (Schroth et al, 1995) but the evidence for tree pathogens is inconsistent (Schroth et al, 2000).
- Lower densities of trees compared with orchards favour increased air circulation which has been shown to reduce the severity of scab by reducing leaf wetness duration (Carisse & Dewdney, 2002).
- Regular cultivations within the crop alleys will incorporate leaf litter into the soil, thus enhancing decomposition and reducing the risk of re-inoculation from overwintered scabbed leaves the following spring.

This research aimed to evaluate an apple/arable agroforestry approach as a sustainable strategy for reducing copper inputs in organic and low input systems using two case studies; Wakelyns Agroforestry, Suffolk, UK (Section 2) and Whitehall Farm, Cambridgeshire, UK (Section3).

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- (v) Impact on management activities (Section 5).

2. Case Study 1: Wakelyns Agroforestry, Suffolk, UK

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Wakelyns Agroforestry, an organic silvoarable research site was established in 1994 on 22.5 ha in eastern England, (52.4°N, 1.4°E, Figure 2.1). There are a number of different agroforestry systems on Wakelyns, including a 2ha apple/arable agroforestry system. Within this system, a diverse mix of 21 varieties of apple trees on MM111 rootstock are interspersed with 7 timber species (small-leaved lime (*Tilia cordata*), hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*), wild cherry (*Prunus avium*), Italian alder (*Alnus cordata*), ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), oak (*Quercus petraea*), sycamore (*Acer pseudoplatanus*), in north/south rows with 12 m-wide crop alleys between adjacent rows (Figure 2.2). Cereals, potatoes, field vegetables and fertility-building leys are grown in rotation within the alleys. The apple trees cover 2.5% of the land area in the 2ha system.

Figure 2.1. Map of southern England showing location of Wakelyns Agroforestry

This design offers the opportunity to increase the spacing among individual trees of a particular species in two dimensions. First, the alley itself separates the rows of trees by 12 m. Second, the tree rows contain eight different tree species, including apple, which are planted as randomised blocks, but with two trees of each species at each planting position. The average distance between adjacent pairs of tree species is about 5 m, so that a single pair of apple trees is represented only once in a 40 m line of trees. This arrangement was designed to mimic the spatial patterns obtained in a mixture of cereal varieties, which has been shown to be a major factor in reducing the rate of spread of fungal diseases among plants (Chin & Wolfe, 1984; Wolfe, 1985). Theoretically, therefore, the apple tree arrangement at Wakelyns should delay the spread of a range of pathogens, and, indeed, pests, relative to a conventional orchard arrangement where the apple host trees are packed more closely in all directions.

Clarkes Lane Orchard, a local modern 0.6 ha organic orchard acted as a benchmark for comparison (:52.3°N, 1.3°E, Figure 2.3). A new orchard was planted on 0.2 ha of the site in 2004/05, which included plums, pears and 19 varieties of apples, planted on M9 rootstock. Trees are spaced 1.5 m within rows and 3 m between rows; rows vary in length up to a maximum of 45 m. Neither system uses copper to control for scab, or any other inputs.

Figure 2.2. Apple and timber silvoarable agroforestry system at Wakelyns Agroforestry. Above - cereals in the crop alleys; below – fertility-building ley in the alleys.

Figure 2.3. Clarkes Lane Orchard

2.1. Methods

The experimental design at Wakelyns consisted of four plots, each plot including two tree rows and the crop alley in between, with 7-10 apple trees in each plot interspersed with timber trees (Figure 2.4). At Clarkes Lane Orchard there were also four plots, each plot consisting of two tree rows and the narrow grass alley in between (Figure 2.5).

Varieties

- | | | | |
|------------------------|----------------------|-----------------------|---------------------|
| 1. Cornish gillyflower | Orleans reinette | 10. St. Albans pippin | Winter pearmain |
| Gooseberry | 6. Broad eyed pippin | Flower of Kent | 15. Kentish pippin |
| 2. Cornish gillyflower | Kentish quorenden | 11. Summer gold | Rev. W. Wilkes |
| Orleans reinette | 7. St. Albans pippin | pippin | 16. John apple |
| 3. Gooseberry | Hawthornden | Bloody ploughman | Devon quorenden |
| Ashmead kernel | 8. Bloody ploughman | 12. Orange goff | 17. Devon quorenden |
| 4. Ashmead kernel | Flower of Kent | Rev. W. Wilkes | Kentish pippin |
| Five crowns | 9. Summer gold | 13. Orange goff | |
| 5. Five crowns | Hawthornden | 14. John apple | |

Figure 2.4. Experimental design at Wakelyns Agroforestry

Figure 2.5. Experimental design at Clarkes Lane Orchard

(i) Yield and quality of apple crop

In autumn 2012 and 2013, all apples harvested from each site were graded as Class I/Class II/processing/waste and weighed per class and variety (Figure 2.6).

Figure 2.6. Harvesting apples at Wakelyns Agroforestry

The following criteria were used for grading the apples (taken from Commission implementing regulation (EU) No 543/2011 available at www.gov.uk):

Class I: Good quality produce, allowing for minor defects such as:

- Areas of slight skin defects not exceeding 2cm in length for defects of elongated shape, or 1cm² of total surface area for other defects except scab which must not extend over more than 0.25cm² cumulative in area,
- Slight shape defects,
- Slight bruising not exceeding 1cm² of total surface area and not discoloured,
- Slight defect in colour,
- Slight defect in development
- Slight russeting.

Class II: Reasonably good quality produce, which may show one or more defects such as:

- Defects in shape,
- Defects in development,
- Defects in colouring,
- Slight bruising not exceeding 1.5cm² in area which may be slightly discoloured,
- Skin defects that don't extend more than 4cm in length for elongated defects or 2.5cm² of total surface area for other defects except scab which mustn't extend over more than 1cm² cumulatively.
- Slight russeting.

Processing/industry: Any other apples that could be used for juicing or cooking.

Waste: Apples with no value at all.

The economics of the system are reported in Section 4.

(ii) Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases.

Pests and diseases were assessed in the plots at three points: small fruits in July 2012 and 2013, large fruits in August 2012 and 2013, and the harvested apples (September to November 2012 and 2013). One sample consisted of 100 plant units chosen randomly from all trees in the plot area (i.e. 100 small developing fruits; 100 large fruits pre-harvest; 100 harvested fruits). Each plant unit was thoroughly inspected for eggs, insects or insect damage and diseases. Pheromone traps were used to assess flight activity of the codling moth (Figure 2.7). One pheromone trap was placed in each plot for ten weeks from end May to August and assessed for codling moth after 5 weeks when the sticky insert and pheromone attractant was replaced and again at the end of 10 weeks.

Figure 2.7. Codling moth pheromone trap in the orchard

(iii) Impact on ecosystem services.

Biodiversity:

Timed transect walks

In 2012 adult bumblebees and butterflies were identified and recorded along a 100m transect, extending 2.5m either side of this line (Westphal et al, 2008). There was one transect per plot, walking adjacent to tree rows. The transects were walked at a rate of 15-20 m min⁻¹ and assessments carried out between 10.00 and 17.00 h only when weather conformed to Butterfly Monitoring Standards (temperature >13°C with at least 60% clear sky, or 17 °C in any sky conditions, no rain, wind speed <5 on the Beaufort scale). The transect walks were not repeated in 2013 as the data produced in 2012 was rather limited due to challenges in timing the field visits to periods of acceptable weather conditions.

Pan traps

This method focused on measuring pollinators and natural enemies. Each cluster of pan traps consisted of one each of UV-bright yellow, white and blue pan traps, suspended from the trees, filled with 400ml water and a drop of detergent (Westphal et al, 2008). Traps were left active for 48 hours and the collected specimens stored in 70% ethanol until identification. There were two clusters of traps per plot i.e. 8 clusters per site, located within a tree row next to apple trees (Figure 2.8). Traps were set mid-May, mid-July and end of August in 2012 and 2013. The invertebrates collected in each pan trap were sorted to order, and their abundances recorded. The Hymenoptera were then sorted to family and the bees (Apoidea) identified to species (2012 only). The wasps were divided into parasitic and predatory morphogroups based on antennal segment numbers.

Figure 2.8. Pan traps in apple tree at Wakelyns Agroforestry

Nylon mesh bag method

The density of predatory mites and insects was estimated with this method (Cuthbertson & Murchie, 2005). A nylon mesh bag (150mm x 150mm of rectangular mesh 7x7mm) containing heat sterilised (48h at 55°C) chopped barley straw was placed in apple trees; 3 bags per tree in 4 apple trees per plot (i.e. 12 bags per plot; 48 bags per system). Straw traps were attached to branches and left for 3 weeks during July (Figure 2.9). The traps were then placed under Tullgren funnels for 24 hours where predatory arthropods were expelled into 70% ethanol. In 2015, mite samples were sent to partners BPI for identification to species.

Figure 2.9. Straw mesh bag in apple tree

Microclimate

Regulation of the microclimate was assessed monthly from April 2012 to December 2013 by measuring air temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, soil moisture and soil temperature. Air temperature (°C), average wind speed over 1 minute and wind chill (°C) were measured at 1.5m above ground using a Kestrel 3500 anemometer. Soil moisture was measured using a HH2 Moisture Meter with the SM300 soil moisture probe from Delta T (average of 3 readings per sample point). Soil temperature (°C) was measured using a push-in soil thermometer. At the Wakelyns site, measurements were taken in the western tree row (adjacent to an apple tree) and in the centre of the alley on one transect per plot. At Clarkes Lane Orchard, measurements were taken within the western tree row in each plot. From mid-May to end of August 2012 data loggers recorded air temperature and relative humidity hourly.

Soil quality

Soil quality was assessed using the Solvita gel system to measure soil CO₂ respiration (Haney et al, 2008), to quantify the impact of management on soil microbial activity as an indicator of soil fertility. Soil samples were taken in early October 2015, from the western tree row and centre of the crop alley in each plot at Wakelyns Agroforestry (i.e. total of four samples from tree rows and four from crop alleys) and in the western tree row in each of the four plots at Clarkes Lane Orchard. At each point, three soil cores were taken at least 10cm apart, and combined to give a composite sample. The samples were sent for analyses to the NRM laboratory using the Soil Health Analytical Package (Cawood Scientific Ltd, 2015). In addition to soil respiration rate (CO₂ burst mg/kg), this also

analysed available phosphorus (mg/l), available potassium (mg/l), available magnesium (mg/l), soil organic matter (LOI %), soil pH, and soil particle size distribution.

Statistical analyses

Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases

Scab levels and incidences of other pests and diseases in the agroforestry and orchard plots in 2012 and 2013 were compared statistically using t-tests, using R version 2.10.0 (R Development Core Team, 2009).

Impact on ecosystem services.

Biodiversity

For the pan trap invertebrate data a general linear mixed model was used (Bouffartigue, 2013). Abundances were log (N+1) transformed. Mixed models were made to find the dependence of the abundance of the main orders, families and species on the treatment (WAF vs CLO), the months (May, July, August) and the interaction between the two. Treatment and months were included as fixed factors (Model I). Another model per taxa was then designed using temperature, relative humidity and the interaction between them as explanatory variables (Model II). Deletion of non-significant parameters was performed to achieve model simplification and only the results of the simpler model are displayed. Finally, a third model integrating the best explanatory variable of each model was designed and compared to the first two using the AIC (Akaike's Information Criterion).

Microclimate

Average wind speed (mph), air temperature (°C), wind chill temperature (°C), soil temperature (°C) and soil moisture (%) in the agroforestry tree rows and crop alleys and orchard were compared statistically using a sequence of one-way ANOVAs on the monthly data, using R version 2.10.0 (R Development Core Team, 2009) with location (WAF tree row, WAF crop alley and CLO) as the fixed factor. Where a significant effect was found, *post-hoc* pairwise comparisons of means were performed using Tukey's HSD test to identify significant differences between locations.

Soil quality

Soil P, K, Mg, SOM, pH and respiration rate data were analysed using a one-way ANOVA with location (WAF tree row, WAF crop alley and CLO) as a fixed factor. Where a significant effect was found, *post-hoc* pairwise comparisons of means were performed using Tukey's HSD test to identify significant differences between locations.

2.2. Results and discussion

(i) Yield and quality of apples

2012

Apple production in England in 2012 was severely affected by heavy rain from April to June and late frosts, with some fruit farmers reporting losses of up to 90% of their crop. In the agroforestry and orchard sites, some varieties failed to set fruit (e.g. Cornish Gillyflower at Wakelyns; Spartan and Winter Gem at the orchard), or had very low fruit set. In addition, high levels of scab impacted on yields at the orchard (see below) and so the resulting total apple yields were very low (Figure 2.10). Yields within the agroforestry were higher; taking into account the fact that apple trees cover only 2.5% of the area (tree plus understory). Comparing yields with standard figures from the Organic Farm Management Handbook (Lampkin et al, 2011/12) by calculating the yield of 100% agroforestry apples (i.e. multiplying by 40), the yields from the agroforestry compare favourably with standard yields (Class I & II: 15.7 t/ha from the agroforestry vs. 14 t/ha from orchards at peak production).

Figure 2.10. Total apple yields (t/ha) from the agroforestry (WAF) and orchard (CLO) sites in 2012. NB. Apple trees account for 2.5% of land area in the agroforestry system.

2013

Apple yields in 2013 were substantially better than in 2012. Yields within the organic orchard were 2.24 t/ha (Class I, II and processing) compared with 0.7215 from the agroforestry (Fig. 2.11. NB. apples account for 2.5% of the agroforestry land area). Comparing yields with standard figures from the Organic Farm Management Handbook (Lampkin et al 2012) by calculating the yield of 100% agroforestry apples (i.e. multiplying by 40), the yields from the agroforestry compare favourably (Class I & II: 19.25 t/ha from the agroforestry vs. 14 t/ha from orchards at peak production).

Figure 2.11. Total apple yields (t/ha) from the agroforestry (WAF) and orchard (CLO) sites in 2013. NB. Apple trees account for 2.5% of land area in the agroforestry system.

(ii) Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases.

Scab

2012

Neither the agroforestry apple trees or orchard trees are sprayed for scab, and so there were high levels of scab in both systems (Fig. 2.12 and 2.13). However, scab levels of both small and large fruits were over twice as high in the orchard compared with the agroforestry site and analyses showed a statistically significant difference (small fruits $t=4.25$, $p<0.01$; large fruits $t=3.44$, $p<0.05$). There were no significant differences between scab levels in the harvested agroforestry and orchard apples though (Table 2.1).

Figure 2.12. Mean scab incidence per plot in the agroforestry (WAF) and orchard (CLO) in 2012

2013

Scab levels of both small, large and harvested fruits were several times higher in the orchard compared with the agroforestry site (Fig. 2.13) although due to wide variation within sites, there was only a significant difference between sites in the small fruits ($t=3.11$, $P<0.05$; Table 2.1).

Figure 2.13 Mean scab incidence per plot in the agroforestry (WAF) and orchard (CLO) in 2013

Table 2.1. P-values of t-tests comparing diseases and pests in the agroforestry and orchard plots

	Small Fruit		Large Fruit		Harvested Fruit	
	2012	2013	2012	2013	2012	2013
Scab	**	*	*	NS	NS	NS
Sawfly damage	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Capsid damage	NS	NS	NS	NS	**	NS
Codling damage	NS	NS	*	**	NS	NS
Aphid damage	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS
Moth damage		NS		*		
Earwig damage						NS
Crack	**	NS	*	NS		
Open flesh	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	
Brown Rot			NS	NS	NS	NS
Sooty blotch						NS

* P≤0.05; ** P<0.01; *** P<0.001, NS = not significant, Blank = no incidences recorded

Other pests and diseases

2012

Secondary pest and disease damage was also recorded (Figures 2.14 to 2.16). There were significantly more cracks in both the small and large apples in the orchard (small apples $t=6.13$, $P<0.01$), perhaps reflecting an erratic supply of water in the orchard. There was a higher incidence of insect damage to small developing fruits by sawflies ($t=-3.29$, $P<0.05$) and to large fruits by codling moths ($t=3.94$, $P<0.03$) in the agroforestry system compared with the orchard (Table 2.1). Interestingly, codling moth damage was then higher in the orchard in the pre-harvest apples (non-significant), which may have been due to differences in the phenology of the moth between the systems. At harvest, capsid damage was significantly higher in the agroforestry apples ($t=-4.57$, $P<0.01$; Figure 2.16).

Figure 2.14. Pest and disease damage to small developing fruit in July 2012.

Figure 2.15. Pest and disease damage to large fruit in August 2012.

Figure 2.16. Pest and disease damage to harvested fruit 2012.

2013

Secondary pest and disease damage was also recorded in 2013 (Figures 2.17 to 2.19). A preliminary consideration of the data suggests that secondary pests were more common in the agroforestry system, with higher levels of sawfly, capsid, aphid and moth damage than in the orchard. However, in the small fruit, statistically significant differences were found only for occurrences of open flesh (likely caused by birds, $t=-4.37$, $P<0.05$, Figure 2.17)). In the large fruit, there were significantly higher levels of aphid damage ($t=-3.17$, $P=0.05$) and moth damage ($t=-2.66$, $P<0.05$) in the agroforestry, and significantly higher levels of codling moth damage in the orchard ($t=8.69$, $P<0.01$, Figure 2.18). There were no significant differences found in the harvested fruit (Figure 2.19).

Figure 2.17. Pest and disease damage to small developing fruit in July 2013.

Figure 2.18. Pest and disease damage to pre-harvest fruit in August 2013.

Figure 2.19. Pest and disease damage to harvested fruit in 2013.

The pheromone traps had higher numbers of codling moths at the orchard in July in both years, while numbers were more even or higher in the agroforestry plots in the August samples (Table 2.2).

Table 2.2. Total number of codling moths recorded in the pheromone traps in 2012 and 2013

	July		August	
	2012	2013	2012	2013
WAF	2	6	14	23
CLO	31	32	13	10

(iii) Impact on ecosystem services (biodiversity, soil health, microclimate) and functionality.

Biodiversity:

Timed transect walks

Bumblebees were recorded on timed transect walks in June, as well as in early and late August (Table 2.3). Due to the cool and wet spring and summer, abundances were low, with very few bees recorded in early August. The data indicates higher abundances and more species of bumblebee within the agroforestry in June compared with the orchard, but due to the low numbers, no statistical analyses were carried out.

Table 2.3. Bumblebee abundance and species diversity recorded on timed transects in June and August 2012. * is an aggregate of *B. terrestris* and *B. lucorum*

Date		<i>Bombus lapidarius</i>	<i>Bombus terrestris*</i>	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	<i>Bombus hortorum</i>	<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	Total abundance	No. species
26.06.12	WAF	5	21	4	1	2	33	5
	CLO	8	16	2	0	0	26	3
02.08.12	WAF	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CLO	1	0	1	0	0	2	2
22.08.12	WAF	2	0	9	0	0	11	2
	CLO	1	1	5	0	0	7	3

Pan traps

2012

By Cathy Bouffartigue, ORC intern and MSc student AgroParisTech. (For more details please see Bouffartigue (2013)).

In 2012 a total of 20,089 individuals were collected, consisting of 12 orders (dominant orders detailed in Table 2.4). The most abundant order was the Coleoptera with 14,946 individuals. Within the Hymenoptera there were 171 bees comprised of 21 species, 129 parasitic wasps and 336 predatory wasps. Statistical analyses using general linear mixed models found no significant difference in total Hymenoptera abundance between the agroforestry and orchard. At the family level, there were significantly more *Lassioglossum* and *Bombus* in the orchard than in the agroforestry, and more predatory and parasitic wasps in the agroforestry (Table 2.5, Figure 2.20).

Table 2.4. Abundance of the main taxa sampled in pan traps in the orchard (CLO) and agroforestry (WAF)

	Coleoptera	Diptera	Heteroptera	Hymenoptera
CLO Total	10297	1879	339	323
May	65	422	2	27
July	10180	742	222	203
August	52	715	115	93
WAF Total	4649	1616	401	329
May	21	422	6	19
July	4590	685	370	180
August	38	509	25	130

Table 2.5. Results of repeated measures analysis of abundances of Apoidea families. NS= not significant and excluded from model, *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001.

Fixed effects	<i>Andrena</i>	<i>Bombus</i>	<i>Lasioglossum</i>
Model I			
Treatment	NS	F=11.76**	F=24.51***
Month	F=11.45***	NS	F= 38.64***
Treatment*Month	NS	NS	F=15.16***
Model II			
Temperature	F= 14.46***	F= 4.22*	F= 10.81**
Relative Humidity	NS	NS	NS
Temperature*Relative humidity	NS	NS	F= 4.38*
AIC			
Model I	71.14	49.59	86.87
Model II	80.02	62.36	154.95
Model III	79.06	57.66	114.76

Figure 2.20. Total abundance of Hymenoptera in the agroforestry (WAF) and orchard (CLO) systems in 2012.

2013

In 2013 a total of 3094 individuals were collected, consisting of 12 orders. The most abundant order was the Diptera with 2026 individuals (Table 2.6). There was a total of 400 Hymenoptera (bees and wasps). All orders were found at higher abundances in the orchard (Table 2.6).

Table 2.6. Abundance of the main taxa sampled in pan traps in the orchard (CLO) and agroforestry (WAF)

	Coleoptera	Diptera	Heteroptera	Hymenoptera
CLO Total	287	1235	83	249
May	12	249	15	16
July	0	470	12	46
August	275	516	56	187
WAF Total	63	791	23	151
May	20	331	9	31
July	1	95	1	12
August	42	365	13	108

Figure 2.21. Abundance of hymenoptera captured in pan traps during the summer of 2013.

Microclimate

Monthly point measurements

There were few significant differences in wind speed between the orchard, tree row and crop alley over the two years of monitoring (Table 2.7), with significant differences detected only in September 2012 (wind speeds higher in the tree row than in the crop alley and orchard), February 2013 (orchard lower than crop alley) and May 2013 (orchard lower than tree row and crop alley; Figure 2.22a). Air temperature and wind chill temperatures were significantly higher in the orchard during the summer months compared with the agroforestry (Table 2.7, Figure 2.22b and 2.22c). Differences in relative humidity were inconsistent, apart from a three month period in the summer of 2013 when RH was significantly lower in the orchard than in the agroforestry (Figure 2.22d). Soil temperatures were higher in the crop alleys than the orchard and tree rows in the summer months in 2012 and 2013, and lower in November and December 2013 (Figure 2.22e). Soil moisture was significantly lower in the orchard in the summer 2012 and 2013 (Figure 2.22f).

Table 2.7. P-values of ANOVA analyses of microclimate data: * P<0.05; ** P<0.01; * P<0.001, NS = not significant; NA = data not available**

Month	Wind Speed	Air Temp	Wind Chill	Relative Humidity	Soil Temp	Soil moisture
Apr-12	NS	*	NS	**	NS	NS
May-12	NS	**	*	***	NS	NS
Jun-12	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS
Jul-12	NS	NS	NS	NS	**	NS
Aug-12	NS	**	**	NS	***	NS
Sep-12	***	**	**	NS	***	NS
Oct-12	NS	**	**	NS	NS	**
Nov-12	NS	NS	NS	***	NS	*
Dec-12	NS	***	NS	NS	NS	*
Jan-13	NS	NS	NS	**	**	**
Feb-13	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	***
Mar-13	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	*
Apr-13	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	***
May-13	**	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Jun-13	NS	NS	NS	NS	**	**
Jul-13	NS	*	*	**	**	*
Aug-13	NS	*	*	*	NS	*
Sep-13	NS	**	*	***	**	**
Oct-13	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Nov-13	NS	NS	NS	**	***	NS
Dec-13	NS	*	NS	NS	**	NA

— TREE — ALLEY — ORCHARD

Figure 2.22. Monthly microclimate measurements at Wakelyns Agroforestry (TREE row and crop ALLEY) and Clarkes Lane ORCHARD.

Data loggers

Figure 2.23 shows the mean daily air temperature (recorded by the data loggers) within the agroforestry tree rows (WAF_temp) and crop alleys (A_WAF_temp) and orchard (CLO_temp) from mid-May to end of August 2012. Temperatures within the orchard were similar to those in the crop alleys of the agroforestry, with lower temperatures recorded within the agroforestry tree rows. Figure 2.24 shows the mean daily relative humidity within the agroforestry tree rows and alleys and the orchard. We expected to find higher relative humidity within the orchard because of the higher density of trees, but the data shows that relative humidity was lower in the orchard than in the agroforestry, perhaps indicating a more exposed site.

Figure 2.23. Mean daily air temperature.

Figure 2.24. Mean daily relative humidity (%).

Soils

The soils at Wakelyns are classified as sandy clay to clay loams, while the soils at Clarkes Lane Orchard have a higher proportion of sand and so are classified as sandy to sandy clay loams. There were no statistically significant differences between soil P, K and Mg in the samples from the Wakelyns tree rows and crop alley and the orchard (Figure 2.25 (a) to (c)). Soil organic matter was significantly different ($F = 9.398$, $P < 0.01$, Figure 2.25(d)) with CLO having lower SOM than the Wakelyns tree row (there was also a borderline difference between the tree row and crop alley at Wakelyns ($P = 0.056$)). Soil pH was significantly lower at CLO than at Wakelyns ($F = 18.9$, $F < 0.001$, Figure 2.25(e)), and soil respiration was significantly lower in the crop alley compared with the tree row at Wakelyns Agroforestry ($F = 7.756$, $P < 0.05$, Figure 2.25(f)).

Figure 2.25. Soil quality in the tree rows and crop alleys at Wakelyns Agroforestry and Clarkes Lane Orchard.

2.3. Summary of Case Study 1: Wakelyns Agroforestry

Apple yields in 2012 were adversely affected by the weather, with low fruit set due to late frosts and heavy rain. Despite this, the yield from the agroforestry system was comparable with standard figures when scaled up from 2.5% land area under apple production to 100% apples, and even at just 2.5% cover, appeared to out-perform the organic orchard used for comparison. In 2013, the yields were higher in both systems (2.24 t/ha from the orchard and 0.72 t/ha from the agroforestry), and again, when scaled up to 100% land cover, the agroforestry apple yields compared well with standard figures (Class I & II: 19.25 t/ha from the agroforestry vs. 14 t/ha from orchards at peak production).

It must be taken into account that the trees within the agroforestry system are on vigorous rootstock and 18 years old, while those in the orchard are on dwarfing rootstock and 8 years old, but it could be argued that both of these systems are in the peak production phase for their rootstock (from 8 years for MM111 and 5 years for M9) and so the comparison at the system level (i.e. agroforestry vs. modern orchard production) is valid.

Although no firm general conclusion can be drawn from this case study, it appears as if there may be indications of a potential positive impact on reducing scab levels within the agroforestry. This could be due to the very low densities of apple trees. Also, that while some varieties may fail to set fruit or have high levels of scab, the high diversity of apple varieties within the agroforestry means that other varieties will have compensate and so buffer against extreme losses of yields. However, further research will be required to confirm this theory.

The impacts of secondary pests and diseases varied between the agroforestry and orchard, with higher levels of sawfly, aphid, capsid and moth damage in the agroforestry apples. Codling moth damage was higher in the pre-harvest orchard apples. This confirms previous research on agroforestry systems that suggested that while some pests are reduced in agroforestry systems, other pest groups (e.g. slugs) may be observed in higher numbers, and concluded that shifts in relative importance of pest groups may present novel management problems and influence crop choice (Griffiths et al, 1998).

While we found no significant difference in total Hymenoptera abundance between the agroforestry and orchard, there were differences at the family level, with significantly more *Lassioglossum* and *Bombus* in the orchard than in the agroforestry, and more predatory and parasitic wasps in the agroforestry. Compared with an orchard, the agroforestry system is subject to more frequent disturbances (relating to crop production) and this may impact on pollinator diversity. In addition, floral resources may be lower in the agroforestry – even when there is a clover fertility-building ley in the crop alleys, these are cut regularly so there are gaps in the provision of flower resources. The orchard is surrounded by a floristically diverse hedgerow, and the grass understorey was not cut during the two years of this study, so this may have provided a stable habitat with consistent floral resources. The higher levels of predators and parasitic wasps in the agroforestry system may reflect a more consistent supply of prey species in the agroforestry.

It was expected that wind speeds would be higher in the agroforestry compared with the orchard

due to the lower density of trees, and the alley design. However, there was no consistent pattern of lower wind speeds in the orchard; the system at Wakelyns is protected to the south by a row of tall poplar trees and this may reduce wind speeds in the agroforestry. Soil temperature was significantly higher in the summer and lower in the winter in the crop alleys, demonstrating the buffering effect of trees on temperature extremes.

The soils in the orchard are sandier than those at Wakelyns so it is difficult to draw any firm conclusions regarding the effects of agroforestry on soil quality. However, it is interesting to note that soil organic matter is lower in the orchard compared with both the tree row and crop alley at Wakelyns, even though the alley is regularly cultivated and cropped. There were no differences between the agroforestry and orchard with regards soil respiration rates, but within the agroforestry system, respiration rates in the tree row were higher than in the alley, perhaps reflecting the more stable nature of the soils under the trees.

While there appear to be a number of potential benefits to integrating apple production within a diverse agroforestry system in terms of production and reduced disease pressure, there are management considerations associated that need to be taken into account. The apple trees cover just 2.5% of the land area, and so are a minor part of the system, and this would probably not be acceptable for large scale apple producers who rely on economies of scale. However, this approach could work well in a diverse, potentially small-scale system such as a market garden, where apples could contribute to direct marketing channels such as vegetable box schemes or farm shops. Having such a wide range of varieties within the system means that harvesting would occur over a longer period. This requires careful planning and may be a challenge for selling to wholesalers if only small amounts are ready at any one time. New approaches to marketing could address this problem, for example, creating mixed bags of varieties, categorizing by taste, e.g. 'sweet' apple bag, or 'sharp' apple bag; or by making more of a feature of the varieties if going into vegetable box schemes e.g. 'apple of the week'.

3. Case study 2: Whitehall Farm

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Whitehall Farm is 100ha arable farm on Grade 1 high organic soil near Peterborough, Cambs (Figure 3.1). Previously managed as an intensive arable system, the eastern half of the farm entered into organic conversion in 2007, while the rest entered conversion in August 2009. In October 2009, 4,500 apple trees, consisting of 13 varieties (9 commercial and 4 traditional) were planted in rows (NE/SW orientation) 27m apart, with 3m spacing of trees within rows. The understorey was sown before tree planting with a 3m band of nectar flower mixtures and legumes. The 24m remaining between rows is cropped on an organic rotation including cereals, vegetables and legume fertility-building leys. Late maturing tree varieties have been chosen to allow harvesting of the alley crops first. Pruning of overhanging branches will develop the trees into a hedge-like structure to minimize damage from machinery in the alleys. There is no local commercial organic orchard to use as a benchmark. Instead we used Willock Farm, a local heritage orchard, as a comparison – this was planted in 2006 on MM106 semi-dwarfing rootstocks, with 200+ heritage varieties, two individual trees of each variety. Trees are planted 7.2m apart, there are no inputs, and the understorey is managed as a hay crop (Figure 3.2).

**Figure 3.1. Apple trees and spring wheat at Whitehall Farm Agroforestry.
Above July 2014, Below September 2014.**

Table 3.1. Apple varieties planted at Whitehall Farm

Variety	No. trees	No. rows/ variety	Scab resistance
Pinova	388	5	R
Fiesta	313	5	MR
Red Devil	184	2	R
Limelight	184	2	R
Red Windsor	540	6	R
Rajka	300	3	R
Falstaff	1100	9	MR
H Russett	300	4	R
Saturn	278	3	R
Bramley	482	5	S
Adams Pearmain	87	1	R
Ashmeads Kernel	87	1	MR
Chivers Delight	84	1	MR
Total	4327	47	

Figure 3.2. Willock Farm orchard. July 2014.

3.1. Methods

At Whitehall Farm, three apple varieties were chosen for inclusion in the research, based on number of replicated rows available, the degree of scab resistance, and the crop in the alley (spring wheat in all). The varieties chosen were the susceptible variety Bramley (Field 7, Figure 3.3a), the moderately resistant variety Falstaff (Field 7, Figure 3.3b) and the resistant variety Red Windsor (Field 2, Figure 3.3c). For each of these varieties, three rows were sampled, with four assessments per tree and with 100 assessments in total per sample, and one (blossoms) or two (small and large apples) samples per row (i.e. three or six samples per variety). Field 11 was used as no-tree control (5.4ha) for comparison of biodiversity and soils (Field 11, Figure 3.4). In the orchard at Willock Farm, we assessed all apple trees, with 4 assessments per tree.

Figure 3.3. Top (a) Bramley; Centre (b) Falstaff and Bottom (c) Red Windsor

Figure 3.4. Map of Whitehall Farm (showing field numbers)

(i) Yield and quality of apples.

In autumn 2014 and 2015, all apples were harvested at Whitehall Farm by commercial pickers and yields per variety obtained. As the apples were destined for juicing, just prior to harvest four apples per tree were graded as Class I/Class II/processing/waste to assess quality.

(ii) Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases.

Following the common protocol developed within Co-Free Task 8.5, pests and diseases were assessed in the plots at three points before harvest: flower buds in May 2014 and 2015, small fruits in July 2014 and 2015, and large fruits just prior to harvest in September 2014 and 2015. One sample consisted of 100 plant units chosen randomly from all trees (4 units per tree) in the plot area (100 blossom clusters; 100 young shoots; 100 large fruits pre-harvest). Each plant unit was thoroughly inspected for eggs, insects or insect damage and diseases.

(iii) Impact on ecosystem services.

Biodiversity

Pan traps

Pan traps were used to assess pollinators and natural enemies. Each cluster of pan traps consisted of one each of UV-bright yellow, white and blue pan traps, suspended from the trees, filled with 400ml water and a drop of detergent. Traps were left active for 48 hours and the collected specimens stored in 70% ethanol until identification. There were ten clusters of traps in each system (agroforestry, orchard and arable). Clusters were located

20m apart along a transect running north-west from the south-eastern corner. There were some difficulties in gaining access to the sites at various times (due to crop harvest etc.) so not all sites were sampled each time. In 2014 traps were set in the arable and agroforestry systems at Whitehall in late April, at all three sites in mid-July and in the agroforestry and orchard only at the beginning of September. In 2015, traps were set at all three sites in May and July. The invertebrates collected in each pan trap were sorted to order, and their abundances recorded.

Soil quality

Soil quality was assessed using the Solvita gel system to measure soil CO₂ respiration (Haney et al, 2008), to quantify the impact of management on soil microbial activity as an indicator of soil fertility. Soil samples were taken in early October 2015. Samples were taken on transects running NW to SE across the arable field and agroforestry field at Whitehall Farm, and the orchard at Willock Farm. Five samples were taken in the arable field and orchard, and ten within the agroforestry field, with five taken in the middle of the crop alleys and five within the tree rows. At each point, three soil cores were taken at least 10cm apart, and combined to give a composite sample. The samples were sent for analyses to the NRM laboratory using the Soil Health Analytical Package (Cawood Scientific Ltd, 2015). In addition to soil respiration rate (CO₂ burst mg/kg), this also analysed available phosphorus (mg/l), available potassium (mg/l), available magnesium (mg/l), soil organic matter (LOI %), soil pH, and soil particle size distribution.

Statistical analyses

Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases

Scab levels and incidences of other pests and diseases in the three variety plots at Whitehall and Willock Farm orchard plots in 2014 and 2015 were compared statistically using one-way ANOVAs with 'treatment' (Bramley, Falstaff, Red Windsor, Orchard) as a fixed factor, using R version 2.10.0 (R Development Core Team, 2009). Where a significant effect was found, *post-hoc* pairwise comparisons of means were performed using Tukey's HSD test to identify significant differences between treatments.

Soil quality

Soil P, K, Mg, SOM, pH and respiration rate data were analysed using a one-way ANOVA with 'treatment' (Bramley, Falstaff, Red Windsor, Orchard) as a fixed factor, using R version 2.10.0 (R Development Core Team, 2009). Where a significant effect was found, *post-hoc* pairwise comparisons of means were performed using Tukey's HSD test to identify significant differences between treatments.

3.2. Results and discussion

(i) Yield and quality of apple and arable crops (including profit margins).

Tree rows account for 10% land area with 85 trees/ha; scaling up to 100% apples, yields in 2014 ranged from 0.25 t/ha to 5.95 t/ha and in 2015 from 1.36 t/ha to 15.18 t/ha (Table 3.2), which compares with standard yields for 5 year old orchard of 3 t/ha and an organic orchard in peak production (6-11 years) of 14 t/ha (Lampkin et al 2014). There was a wide range of yields from different varieties and in the two years, with two of the low yielding varieties (Falstaff, Bramley) in the same field, which may indicate problems with pollination or mineral deficiency although these two varieties also had high levels of scab in 2014. There was a higher proportion of processing apples in 2014 compared with 2015 (Figures 3.5 and 3.6).

Table 3.2. Yields of apples in the agroforestry system at Whitehall Farm, 2014 and 2015

Variety	Average kg / tree		Agroforestry 85 trees/ha t/ha		100% apples t/ha	
	2014	2015	2014	2015	2014	2015
Pinova	2.71	3.35	0.23	0.28	2.30	2.85
Fiesta	3.12	1.60	0.27	0.14	2.65	1.36
Red Devil	2.85	4.35	0.24	0.37	2.42	3.70
Limelight	2.99	5.43	0.25	0.46	2.54	4.62
Red windsor	1.44	4.63	0.12	0.39	1.22	3.94
Rajka	7.00	7.67	0.60	0.65	5.95	6.52
Falstaff	0.55	3.91	0.05	0.33	0.47	3.32
H Russett	2.25	7.25	0.19	0.62	1.91	6.16
Saturn	0.29	4.86	0.02	0.41	0.25	4.13
Bramley	0.41	4.36	0.03	0.37	0.35	3.71
Adams Pearmain	6.90	9.48	0.59	0.81	5.87	8.06
Ashmeads Kernel	1.72	4.60	0.15	0.39	1.46	3.91
Chivers Delight	1.79	17.86	0.15	1.52	1.52	15.18

Figure 3.5. Percentage of each class in pre-harvested fruits 2014

Figure 3.5. Percentage of each class in pre-harvested fruits 2015

(ii) Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases.

Scab

2014

There were high levels of scab in the Bramley and Falstaff varieties in the agroforestry, despite Falstaff being a moderately resistant variety (Table 3.3, Figure 3.6). The Red Windsor apples maintained their resistance to scab. Levels of scab in the orchard were just under 20%. Analysis of variance identified a highly significant difference between all samples in both the small fruit (F=93.54, P<0.001, Figure 3.6) and large fruit (F=279.9, P<0.001). This preliminary data suggests that an agroforestry approach *per se* is not successful at reducing scab levels, and that varietal diversity may be more important (as seen at Wakelyns Agroforestry and Willock Farm orchard).

Table 3.3. P-values of ANOVAs comparing diseases and pests in the agroforestry and orchard plots

	Small Fruit		Large Fruit	
	2014	2015	2014	2015
Scab	***	***	***	***
Crack	***	NS	**	***
Sawfly damage	*	***	NS	NS
Puncture hole	*		NS	
Capsid damage	***	***	***	NS
Codling damage	***		***	NS
Open flesh	NS	*	***	***
Aphid damage	NS	**	*	*
Brown Rot	NS		***	***
Moth damage	***	NS	***	***
Earwig damage				***

* P≤0.05; ** P<0.01; *** P<0.001, NS = not significant, Blank = no incidences recorded

Figure 3.6. Mean scab incidence per plot at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard in July and September 2014

Figure 3.7. Mean scab incidence per plot at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard in July and September 2015

2015

Scab levels were overall lower in 2015, although analyses found a significant difference in both the small fruit ($F=50.93$, $P<0.001$) and large fruit ($F=193.7$, $P<0.001$); this difference was due to much higher levels recorded in the Falstaff plots (Figure 3.7).

Secondary pests and diseases

2014

There were significant differences in levels of other pests and diseases in the blossoms in 2014 (Table 3.3) with higher levels of caterpillars and caterpillar damage in Bramley and Willock blossoms compared with Falstaff and Red Windsor (Figure 3.8). Winter moth caterpillars were found more frequently at Willock orchard compared with Red Windsor ($F=4.04$, $P<0.05$), and tortrix moths caterpillars more frequent in the Bramley and Willock blossoms ($F=10.58$, $P<0.01$). Pollen beetles were also found more frequently at Willock Orchard compared with Whitehall ($F=16.77$, $P<0.001$, Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8. Blossom pests in the plots at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard in May 2014.

A range of secondary pests and diseases were recorded in the agroforestry and orchard systems in 2014 (Figures 3.9 and 3.10, Table 3.3). Moth damage was common in the Bramley and Falstaff apples, as were open flesh wounds caused by insects and/or birds, while Red Windsor suffered high levels of capsid damage. This may reflect the potential conflict in sowing wildflower mixtures under trees to encourage pollinators into the open arable landscape but causing an increase in capsid damage as a result of the flowering plants encouraging higher populations of capsids. In both the small and large fruit, cracks were more frequent at Willock Orchard (small fruit $F=10.2$, $P<0.001$, large fruit, $F=7.41$, $P<0.01$, Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.9. Pest damage in small fruits in the plots at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard July 2014.

Figure 3.10. Pest damage in large fruits in the plots at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard September 2014.

2015

There were significant differences in levels of other pests and diseases in the blossoms in 2015 (Table 3.3) similar to 2014, with higher levels of caterpillar damage in Bramley and Willock blossoms compared with Falstaff and Red Windsor ($F=11.58$, $P<0.001$, Figure 3.11). Tortrix moths caterpillars were more frequent in the Bramley blossoms ($F=24.99$, $P<0.001$).

Blossoms 2015

Figure 3.11. Blossom pests in the plots at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard in May 2015.

In the developing fruits, sawfly damage was the main problem, despite the removal of infected fruit in the agroforestry systems in June 2015, with highest levels in the Willock and Falstaff small apples ($F=39.71$, $P<0.001$, Figure 3.12). In the large fruit, Bramley apples suffered from higher levels of moth damage ($F=25.59$, $P<0.001$) and earwig damage ($F=79.99$, $P<0.001$, Figure 3.13).

Small Fruits 2015

Figure 3.12. Pest damage in small fruits in the plots at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard July 2015.

Large Fruits 2015

Figure 3.13. Pest damage in large fruits in the plots at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm orchard September 2015.

(iii) Impact on ecosystem services

Biodiversity

Table 3.4 shows the abundance of invertebrates collected during 2014; preliminary consideration of the data suggests that while invertebrate abundance is lower in the orchard, there is little difference between the agroforestry and arable systems. In 2015, abundances of all taxa except the hymenoptera were higher in the agroforestry (Table 3.5).

Table 3.4. Abundance of the main taxa sampled in pan traps in the agroforestry, arable field and orchard in 2014

2014	Coleoptera	Diptera	Heteroptera	Hymenoptera
Whitehall Arable Total	4946	3261	38	206
May	4884	2524	26	63
July	62	737	12	143
August	na	na	na	na
Whitehall Agroforestry Total	5199	2782	153	495
May	5023	1723	131	323
July	55	524	10	149
August	121	535	12	23
Willock Orchard Total	26	633	5	109
May	na	na	na	na
July	5	287	1	33
August	21	346	4	76

Table 3.5. Abundance of the main taxa sampled in pan traps in the agroforestry, arable field and orchard in 2015

2015	Coleoptera	Diptera	Heteroptera	Hymenoptera
Whitehall Arable Total	3436	1012	557	290
May	36	608	5	53
July	3400	404	552	237
Whitehall Agroforestry Total	>5121	779	538	258
May	121	472	1	87
July	>5000	307	537	171
Willock Orchard Total	1464	483	62	517
May	562	227	2	434
July	902	256	60	83

Soil quality

The soils at Whitehall Farm and Willock Farm are quite different, with Whitehall soils being peaty clay (in the arable field) to clay loam (in the agroforestry field), while Willock Farm has heavy to medium clay to clay loams, so it is difficult to draw any firm conclusions regarding soil quality. There were statistically significant differences between soil P, K and Mg in the samples from the orchard and from the arable and agroforestry samples, with lower P ($F=19.06$, $P<0.001$) and higher K ($F=8.462$, $P<0.01$) and Mg ($F=59.0$, $P<0.001$) in the orchard (Figure 3.14 (a) to (c)). Soil organic matter was significantly lower in the orchard ($F=163.1$, $P<0.001$, Figure 3.14(d)). Soil pH was significantly lower at in the orchard than at Whitehall Farm ($F=6.84$, $F<0.01$, Figure 3.14(e)), and soil respiration was significantly lower in the orchard ($F=3.638$, $P<0.05$, Figure 3.14(f)).

Figure 3.14. Soil quality in the orchard, agroforestry and arable fields.

3.3. Summary of Case Study 2: Whitehall Farm

The agroforestry system at Whitehall Farm is much more commercial than that at Wakelyns Agroforestry in Case Study 1, in terms of design and scale. Considering that the apple trees at Whitehall were planted only in 2009 and so the system is still establishing and developing, the apple yields look promising, with some varieties performing much better than others. The economics of the system is discussed in more detail in Section 4.

Scab was recorded at quite high levels, particularly in 2014, and in one variety (Falstaff) in 2015, although the resistant variety Red Windsor maintained its resistance. However, the apple varieties studied seemed to perform poorly, while other varieties in the system yielded well and had fewer pests and diseases, which demonstrated the value of planting a wide range of varieties. The varieties were planted in blocks, which is likely to have facilitated the spread of pests and diseases, despite the crop alleys in between tree rows. It may therefore be better to mix varieties within the rows and fields, although this then becomes a challenge to manage and harvest efficiently.

Encouraging pollinators in the agroforestry by establishing a diverse floral mix in the tree row understorey has obviously been successful, although there may be a trade off in terms of managing the understorey to reduce weed pressure and allowing species to flower. Another potential conflict is an increase in capsid damage as a result of the flowering plants encouraging higher populations of capsids, as was recorded in the Red Windsor apples in 2014. In the long term, it may be difficult to maintain flowering species in the understorey sward where they may be outcompeted by grasses.

In conclusion, this case study suggests that an agroforestry approach *per se* is not successful at reducing scab levels. However, if combined with careful selection of resistant varieties and, if possible, mixed planting of varieties, the other benefits that agroforestry brings, particularly to arable systems, may make this approach attractive to arable farmers looking to diversify their enterprises or protect their farms against environmental problems.

4. Economics of agroforestry-based apple production

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4.1. Introduction

An inevitable question about any farming system is whether it is profitable and therefore able to contribute to the farm's economic survival. The pattern of cash-flows can also be important: for some farmers a large initial capital investment may not be possible even if later returns would make such an investment highly desirable.

Economic studies of agroforestry systems have shown that financial benefits are a consequence of increasing the diversity and productivity of the systems, influenced by market and price fluctuations of timber, livestock and crops. However, studies of systems combining arable and apple production in the UK have not been carried out so far.

Compared with exclusively forestry land use, agroforestry practices are able to recoup initial costs more quickly due to the income generated from the agricultural component (Rigueiro-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2008). Fernández-Núñez *et al.* (2007, in Rigueiro-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2008) carried out an assessment of initial investments and establishment costs of forestry, agriculture and agroforestry in the Atlantic area of Spain. They found that establishing agroforestry required higher initial investment than the agricultural and forestry systems due to higher initial inputs, but over a 30 year period, profitability per hectare was higher in the agroforestry system than in the exclusively livestock (17%) or forestry (53%) systems. When environmental and ecological benefits were included in the evaluation, the profitability of the agroforestry system was even higher.

In silvoarable systems, annual returns from crops produced between tree rows can offset plantation establishment costs. Valuable timber trees such as black walnut were once raised as a retirement crop; farmers would sell a mature timber stand to fund their retirement (Scott & Sullivan, 2007). High value timber trees such as black walnut are not ready for harvest until decades after establishment; integrating crops and/or livestock into the system can produce economic value for at least the first twenty years after establishment. Modelling of economic returns from a black walnut alley cropping system in Midwestern USA highlighted the importance of system design and management for maximising productivity (Benjamin *et al.*, 2000). Systems with widely-spaced tree rows (12.2m between tree rows) were predicted to be more profitable than both closely-spaced (8.5m between tree rows) designs and walnut plantations, while root-pruning increased economic returns by extending the period of profitable crop production within the rotation. All agroforestry systems were modelled as having higher rates of returns than monocropping systems (Benjamin *et al.*, 2000).

Doyle and Waterhouse (2008) reviewed studies of the economics of UK agroforestry systems and found a wide range of results, with some studies reporting equivalent or higher returns from agroforestry, e.g. agroforestry yielding 86-108% of the returns from hill sheep farming on improved

land in the west of Scotland (Sibbald, 1990, in Doyle and Waterhouse, 2008); poplar agroforestry yielding long-term economic returns up to 125% of those from sheep farming alone (Willis *et al*, 1993, in Doyle and Waterhouse, 2008); and in a large-scale agroforestry trial in the Highlands of Scotland on a hill sheep farm, income net of costs increased by 30% compared with sheep rearing alone, in the first year of operation (Waterhouse *et al*, 2002, in Doyle and Waterhouse, 2008). Other studies recorded lower rates of returns from agroforestry: in Wales, Thomas (1990, in Doyle and Waterhouse, 2008), reported economic returns of cereal-grass-poplar agroforestry as 52-65% compared with farming alone; and Thomas and Willis (2000, in Doyle and Waterhouse, 2008) projected returns from agroforestry ranging from 76-90% of the returns from hill sheep farming in Scotland, and 85-98% of the returns of lowland cereal farming in southern England. The studies showed that the potential profitability of agroforestry depends on a number of factors including tree species, land type, assumptions regarding the impact over time of canopy closure on the production of the understorey crop and the choice of the discount rate (Doyle and Waterhouse, 2008). None of these studies, however, included fruit trees as the tree component, and it is expected that such systems would differ considerably from timber-based agroforestry.

The effect of grants on profitability and feasibility of agroforestry systems in Europe was explored in a bio-economic model 'FarmSAFE' developed by Graves *et al* (2007). While silvoarable systems were often the most profitable system (compared with arable and forestry systems) at landscape test sites in France, Spain and the Netherlands under a 'no grants' scenario, a pre-2005 grant regime based on direct area payments, and a post-2005 grant regime associated with the single farm payment scheme changed the profitability of silvoarable systems compared with arable and forestry systems, with some agroforestry systems becoming less profitable (Graves *et al.*, 2007). For example, in the Netherlands, losing arable land for slurry manure application made changing land use to agroforestry uncompetitive.

As can be seen from the above discussion, it is difficult to discuss the economics of agroforestry because there is such a wide range of systems covered by the term: silvoarable systems and silvopastoral systems, systems that use timber trees, short rotation coppice or fruit trees. There is also a wide range of policy environments across Europe some of which are more supportive of agroforestry and therefore provide grants that may aid in covering costs and others that are less supportive. Market conditions can also vary with premia being available in some regions or for some systems and not for others. Comparing systems is also difficult due to the different timescales involved e.g. in comparing a fruit tree based system with one using slow growing timber trees. As a result of this huge variability it is unlikely that results can be generalised to all agroforestry, but rather should focus on specific systems.

The remainder of this section is focused on an agroforestry system based in the East of England which combines apple trees with arable production (wheat), using two approaches to examine economic performance; a simple Net Present Value (NPV), and FarmSAFE (a model specifically developed to determine and compare the profitability of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems at a farm and a landscape-scale, which also uses the NPV approach).

4.2. Net Present Value Calculation

Net Present Value (NPV) calculations are widely used investment appraisal methods (ICAEW, 2006). The basic theory behind an NPV calculation is that money received in the present is worth more than the same amount of money received in the future (due to inflation, lost opportunities for investment, etc.). This is sometimes known as the “time value of money”. It is possible to calculate the “present value” of a future cashflow (in or out of a business) by estimating a “discount rate” which is used to reduce the future cashflow to a value which is felt to represent what it would be worth if it was received now (see Box 1).

Box 1: Present value

$$\text{Present value of a cashflow} = \frac{R_t}{(1+i)^t}$$

Where:

R_t is the net cashflow (income minus costs) at time t

i is the discount rate

e.g. a net cashflow of £100 at year 2 with a discount rate of 4% (i.e. 0.04) would be calculated as:

$$\text{present value of cashflow} = \frac{£100}{1.04^2} = £92.46$$

An investment can be evaluated, therefore, by considering all of its cashflows, income and outgoings, into the future (usually for its expected lifespan), estimating the present value of those cashflows and then summing those present values to give the net present value (see Box 2). A positive NPV implies that the investment is profitable; a negative NPV implies that the investment is loss-making (and therefore should be avoided). Two different investments can be compared by comparing their NPVs directly if they cover the same period. An “annual equivalent” to the NPV can be calculated which essentially takes the total NPV and using the period of the investment calculates an annual amount to help the investor see what their equivalent annual income would be from the investment (see Box 3). If two competing investments cover different time periods then calculating the annual equivalent income from each allows them to be compared directly. It is, however, worth noting that this does not mean that the investment will pay out this income each year and, in fact, in some years an investment may involve only costs and not may not produce an income at all, therefore the cashflow implications should be considered as well as the overall profitability.

It can be difficult to compare agroforestry to, for instance, standard arable cropping because agroforestry tends to involve a much higher initial establishment cost and then the tree element may not produce any income for several years whereas the arable system involves a much tighter timescale for both costs and income so comparison of cashflows from a silvoarable agroforestry system in one particular year with an arable system in the same year may give a false idea of the actual comparison over the lifetime of the agroforestry system. The NPV approach is useful for evaluating the economics of agroforestry because it allows comparison of agroforestry with standard arable systems by calculating the NPV of the agroforestry system and its annual equivalent then comparing the annual equivalent with the annual income from arable crops. It also means that

a comparison could be made between a timber-based agroforestry system and an apple-production system (which again have different patterns of cashflow with the timber only system producing the income at the very end of the trees' lifetimes) helping a farmer to decide which would best suit them. The NPV calculation highlights when cashflows arrive as well as their net present value and so can help make a decision about whether the business can cope with one large inflow of cash only at the end of the lifetime or whether a more spread out series of smaller inflows is more desirable.

Box 2: Net present value

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{t=N} \frac{R_t}{(1+i)^t}$$

Where N is the total number of periods (e.g. years) of the investment.

e.g. an investment costs an initial £300 at time t=0. It then produces a net income of £80 per year for t=1 to 5. The discount rate is 4%. Is it worth making the investment?

$$NPV = \frac{-300}{1.04^0} + \frac{80}{1.04^1} + \frac{80}{1.04^2} + \frac{80}{1.04^3} + \frac{80}{1.04^4} + \frac{80}{1.04^5}$$

$$NPV = -300 + 76.92 + 73.96 + 71.12 + 68.38 + 65.75$$

$$NPV = 56.13$$

So the investment returns a (small) profit and is worth making.

NPV example – Whitehall Farm

Stephen Briggs of Whitehall farm (Case Study 2) provided the data necessary to carry out an NPV calculation for his agroforestry system, an organic apple-arable silvoarable system in Cambridgeshire. The system was initially established in 2009 with a view to preventing wind erosion by providing wind breaks (see Section 3 for more details). The understorey is sown with a wildflower pollen/nectar mix which attracts pollinators and allows the system to receive Higher Level Stewardship (HLS) agri-environment payments which make it more profitable. The trees are apple trees which produce apples for sale mainly through wholesale and which also provide a small amount for juicing.

Stephen Briggs provided data on the establishment costs of the agroforestry, the past, present (2014) and anticipated yields of the apples and the income and costs of the apples in 2014. He also provided data on the income and costs associated with the wheat crop planted in the tree alleys in 2014 (and comparative costs for a non-agroforestry wheat crop, which were in fact identical). The data provided are listed in full below (labour costs were split into own labour and contractor costs where appropriate):

1. Tree establishment costs
 - Cultivation
 - Seeding
 - Rolling
 - Seed costs (understorey)
 - Trees
 - Guards
 - Wooden posts
 - Ties
 - Mipex (weed control fabric)
 - Planting labour
 - Re-guarding
 - Additional canes
2. Tree income
 - Income from wholesale
 - Income from juicing
3. Tree costs
 - Weed control (including labour, fuel, maintenance of machinery)
 - Pruning
 - Harvesting
 - Sales (transport; juicing, pasteurising and filtering)
4. Wheat income
 - Income from sale of wheat (yield times price per tonne)
5. Wheat costs
 - Land preparation
 - Seed costs
 - Seeding/planting costs
 - Manuring/fertiliser costs

- Weed control costs
 - Harvesting costs
 - Storage costs
 - Other costs
6. Capital investment (specialised machinery purchased)
 7. Income from agri-environment schemes e.g. SFP (single farm payment) and HLS (higher level scheme)

The NPV calculation assumed a 15 year lifetime for the agroforestry system (based on the likely lifetime of the apple trees). The data for 2014 were used to estimate cash inflows and outflows in other years (pre 2014 and post 2014) based on the following assumptions:

1. Assume the same proportion of apples will go for wholesale (85.7%) and juicing (14.3%) in all future years.
2. Assume 2% inflation annually on all incomes and costs (including income from Single Farm Payment and Higher Level Stewardship).
3. Assume yield per hectare and area of wheat is unchanged year on year.

The apple yield in previous years was given and an estimate of apple yields into the future was made (as the apple yields will change over time as the trees mature and then age).

A discount factor of 4% was used as this figure has been used in previous NPV appraisals of agroforestry systems (Graves *et al.*, 2007) and so this allows comparison with previous research and is a suitable figure for use in discounting agroforestry cashflows.

The calculation was carried out using a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and yielded a NPV of £754,818 for the system or £14,516 per hectare. The annual equivalent was £31,400 or £604 per hectare. Thus it can be seen that the agroforestry system is profitable. The spreadsheet also highlights the reliance on subsidies and agri-environmental payments. In 2014 the income from the single farm payment and HLS is 66% of the total margin. This highlights the contribution that an agroforestry system can make to the environment if it is set up with that in mind (e.g. as in this case, by sowing the tree understorey with a pollen/nectar mixture of wildflowers) but also the fact that such systems are vulnerable to agri-environmental policy changes.

The NPV calculation can also be used to investigate the impact if the agroforestry system was replaced with a fully arable (all wheat) system or with a system that only produced apples. Stephen Briggs confirmed that the costs and incomes for wheat in his non-agroforestry fields were the same as for the wheat in his agroforestry system. Thus, using the same figures as previously but removing the apple incomes and expenses and assuming that the wheat yield and expenses remain the same (and scaling up yields and costs from 48.1ha to 52ha), it is possible to recalculate the NPV. Doing so yielded an NPV of £866,019 or £16,654 per hectare. The annual equivalent was £36,026 or £693 per hectare. This suggests that the wheat-only system would be more profitable than the agroforestry system. However, this had assumed that the area would still be eligible for an HLS payment. Since the agroforestry system (especially the use of a wildflower pollen/nectar mix in the understorey) was designed to qualify for HLS payments it is plausible that the area would not be eligible if it was altered to arable-only production. In the case that the site is not eligible for HLS or an alternative agri-environment payment (e.g. the organic entry level scheme – OELS) the NPV would reduce to

£468,142 or £9,003 per hectare with an annual equivalent of £19,475 or £375 per hectare which would represent a substantial reduction in income. It is likely that the income would lie somewhere between these two extremes as it is unlikely that the site would still qualify for the higher level scheme without the additional environmental benefits conferred by the agroforestry but it is likely that it may still be able to qualify for a scheme such as OELS and so still gain some additional income from agri-environment schemes. In such a case it is likely that it would be less profitable than the agroforestry but closer in value to it.

Similarly to the above, the NPV calculation can also be used to investigate the impact if the agroforestry system was converted to an apple orchard. It is more difficult to do this than was the case with the wheat above as Stephen Briggs does have arable fields outside the agroforestry system and so could confirm that there was no difference in costs or incomes from these but the only apple production on his farm is based in the agroforestry. Assuming that the tree densities remain the same and that all costs and incomes simply scale up linearly as the planted area increases from 3.9ha to 52ha, the apple-only system (including an HLS payment) gives an NPV of -£372,230 or -£7,158 per hectare and an annual equivalent of -£15,485 or -£298 per hectare. This suggests that the apple-only system would be loss-making. However, the assumption that tree densities would remain the same and that costs and incomes would scale linearly may be too simplistic, for instance it may be possible to increase tree densities in the non-agroforestry system. Thus, it is possible that the apple-only system could be made profitable but it appears that it is unlikely that it would be as profitable as the agroforestry system without major changes to the operation.

4.3. FarmSAFE

FarmSAFE is one of the models developed within a European Commission project called ‘Silvoarable Agroforestry for Europe’ (SAFE). The aim of the project was to increase the understanding of temperate silvoarable agroforestry relative to conventional arable and forestry systems. The FarmSAFE model was developed to determine and compare the profitability of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems at a farm and a landscape-scale (Graves et al, 2006; Graves et al, 2009; Graves et al, 2011). The FarmSAFE model can be used simultaneously to examine the profitability of different arable, forestry or agroforestry systems on four land types based on an annual time-step for tree rotations up to 60 years (Graves *et al.*, 2006).

The ‘plot-scale’ (or one-hectare-scale) analysis assumes that a specific system (i.e. arable, forestry or silvoarable agroforestry) is undertaken completely across a specified area. When an arable system is compared with another arable system, the analysis is often based on gross margins (revenue minus variable costs). By contrast, the economic analysis of forestry and agroforestry systems typically include the costs of machinery and labour which are not included in gross margins. FarmSAFE therefore includes “assignable fixed costs” such as labour and machinery in its calculations. If these are included then it is possible to compare the arable, forestry and silvoarable enterprises in terms of the net margin per hectare (Graves *et al.*, 2006).

Farm-scale analysis allows the simulation of the impact of arable, forestry or agroforestry enterprises on a specified farm. Factors such as fixed costs and taxation status are included for this. Each land unit may support one arable, one forestry and one agroforestry system. For the farm-scale analysis, FarmSAFE can use up to four land units, representing different land types or levels of productivity. Thus, up to 12 different systems (four agroforestry, four forestry, and four arable systems) can be simulated within FarmSAFE (Graves *et al.*, 2006).

To account for the change in the value of money during the lifetime of a project, financial values can be discounted over time. The results for each system are then expressed in terms of a net present value (NPV), at a specified discount rate. At the plot-scale, the model assumes that the forestry and agroforestry enterprises are planted in the first year of the project (i.e. year 1). However, a farm-scale analysis might include tree establishment in a range of years. In FarmSAFE, this can be done as irregular single-date plantings or as regular phased plantings (Graves *et al.*, 2006). The net present value is calculated using the equation shown in Box 2 with the cash flow defined as the revenue less variable and assignable costs. In addition, to allow comparison between systems with different rotation lengths, the model can also calculate an infinite NPV (Graves *et al.*, 2011). The infinite NPV is defined as shown in Box 3. It can then be expressed as an annuity (i.e. an annual amount based on the infinite NPV) which is known in the model as an “equivalent annual amount or EAV). The formula for calculating the EAV is also shown in Box 3.

Box 3: Infinite net present value and equivalent annual value

$$NPV_{\text{infinite}} = NPV \frac{(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1}$$

Where *i* is the discount rate and *n* is the rotation period in years.

$$EAV = NPV_{\text{infinite}} \times i$$

FarmSAFE is a Microsoft Excel workbook that has over 50 worksheets and charts (Graves *et al.*, 2006). Data for the yields, costs and revenues of different systems can be entered into spreadsheets for arable, agroforestry and forestry systems. The user can then select which systems they want to model and compare. Figure 4.1 shows the structure of the model.

Figure 4.1. Schematic representation of FarmSAFE economic model, showing the eight principal worksheets (from Graves *et al.*, 2006).

The FarmSAFE model allows the user to test the sensitivity of the outputs to specific inputs (e.g. grants, prices) using user-defined changes to the value of the inputs. Alternatively the effect of a gradual change in a specific input (e.g. if the price of labour is expected to increase over the lifetime of the tree-component of the agroforestry system) can also be modelled.

Modification of FarmSAFE

The existing version of FarmSAFE did not include apple tree systems (the agroforestry systems that were included were timber systems) and so the model needed to be modified to include apple production. The apples were included as a tree by-product and no timber value was taken. The HLS payment was treated as a benefit derived from the trees and so included as a tree grant covering the area of the agroforestry system.

FarmSAFE example

The same input data were used as for the simple NPV calculation. However, the FarmSAFE model requires more detail in terms of breakdown of costs e.g. rather than a pruning cost it requires to know the time taken pruning and the labour cost per hour, rather than a seeding cost for the tree understorey it requires the seed rate (kg seed per hectare) and the seed value (£/kg). In this way the FarmSAFE model is more adaptable i.e. the model used here could then be adapted to see how the same system would work in e.g. France as the timings and seeding/fertilising/crop protection rates would be likely to remain the same but labour costs and seed prices might change. It also allows testing of the sensitivity of the economics to changes in labour costs or commodity values. Where possible costs were split in this way but where information was insufficient to do then the total cost was used. A discount factor of 5% was used.

There were some differences between the FarmSAFE model and the simple NPV described above. The simple NPV includes the cost of a mower and cutter as it was purchased especially for the use in the agroforestry system, however, for comparison with other agroforestry systems within FarmSAFE it was not included in that model as no other capital machinery costs have been included in the other systems already modelled in FarmSAFE. Similarly, in the simple NPV calculation 85.72% of the apples were sold to wholesale and 14.28% went for juicing and the costs of juicing and transport were included as well as the revenue from juice sales. This reflects the actual situation that was occurring on the farm. However, for ease of comparison with other systems, the FarmSAFE model treats all apples as having been sold to wholesale as none of the other systems modelled include a post farm-gate, value-added component.

FarmSAFE allows comparison of three systems: arable, agroforestry and forestry. The arable and agroforestry systems were modelled based on actual data from Whitehall Farm. As there was no comparison orchard the forestry system was based on simply scaling up the tree component of the agroforestry systems. The limitations of this approach are discussed below.

Results

The results are summarised in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: FarmSAFE results for Whitehall Farm comparing arable, agroforestry and forestry (based on scaling up the tree-component of the agroforestry).

System	NPV with grants (£/ha)	EAV with grants (£/ha)	NPV without grants (£/ha)
Arable	£5773	£556	£3749
Agroforestry	£9045	£871	£2086
Orchard	£-6571	£-633	£-11506

It can be seen from these results that the agroforestry system is the more profitable when the arable system obtains only the single farm payment and the agroforestry system obtains the HLS payment. However, if the incomes and costs are considered without the influence of any grants (i.e. the single farm payment and the HLS payment are removed from the calculations) then the arable system is more profitable.

In these initial results it can be seen that the orchard system is loss-making, even with an HLS payment. However, this is based on a simple scaling up of the tree-component of the agroforestry system and so it may be worth further consideration. For instance, the tree densities in an orchard system may be higher and the yields of apples may also be greater. The initial results shown in Table 4.1 are based on 765 trees per hectare. If the tree densities are increased such that 1500 trees are planted per hectare and they are assumed to have the same yield as the agroforestry trees then the NPV (including grants) becomes worse reducing to -£17,027/ha. This suggests that the establishment costs for a larger number of trees are outweighing the income from the trees. If the tree density is returned to the agroforestry-based value of 765 trees per hectare but the yields are doubled then the NPV (including grants) is somewhat improved giving a value of -£5002/ha. If the price received for the apples also doubles to £236/tonne then the NPV (including grants) becomes positive at £859/ha. In fact it is possible to calculate a break-even price and a break-even yield assuming agroforestry densities. If the tree density and yield are kept at the agroforestry tree-component level then the price received per tonne of apples needs to increase to a value of £383/tonne (i.e. 3.242 times the current value) to reach break-even (the NPV with grants becomes £0). If the tree density and value of the apples are kept at the agroforestry tree-component level then the break even yields are 5.19 times the current yield – this suggests that at peak performance the trees must be yielding 19.76 tonnes/ha. To ascertain whether any of these break-even figures are realistic they were compared with values in John Nix's Farm Management pocketbook 2015 (Nix, 2015) and the 2014 Organic Farm Management handbook (Lampkin et al, 2014). The Organic Farm Management handbook suggests yields at peak production of 16 tonnes/ha and prices for Grade I/II apples of £1.40/kg or £1040 per tonne which suggests that the break-even price should be achievable although the yield may fall short of the break-even yield. Nix's Farm Management Pocketbook suggests a yield of 15-55 tonnes/ha for dessert apples and 24-50 tonnes/ha for culinary apples and prices of £525/tonnes to £895/tonne for dessert apples and £265-£525/tonne for culinary apples. This suggests that under a conventional orchard system, which would admittedly have different costs, the break-even price and yield would both be achievable.

4.4. Discussion and conclusion

An inevitable question about any farming system is whether it is profitable and therefore able to contribute to the farm's economic survival. The pattern of cash-flows can also be important: for some farmers a large initial capital investment may not be possible even if later returns would make such an investment highly desirable.

Economic studies of agroforestry systems have shown that financial benefits are a consequence of increasing the diversity and productivity of the systems, influenced by market and price fluctuations of timber, livestock and crops. However, studies of systems combining arable and apple production in the UK have not been carried out so far.

This section focused on an agroforestry system based in the East of England which combines apple trees with arable production (wheat), using two approaches to examine economic performance; a simple Net Present Value (NPV), and FarmSAFE (a model specifically developed to determine and compare the profitability of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems at a farm and a landscape-scale, which also uses the NPV approach).

The basic theory behind an NPV calculation is that money received in the present is worth more than the same amount of money received in the future (due to inflation, lost opportunities for investment, etc.). This is sometimes known as the "time value of money". It is possible to calculate the "present value" of a future cashflow (in or out of a business) by estimating a "discount rate" which is used to reduce the future cashflow to a value which is felt to represent what it would be worth if it was received now. An investment can be evaluated, therefore, by considering all of its cashflows, income and outgoings, into the future (usually for its expected lifespan), estimating the present value of those cashflows and then summing those present values to give the net present value. A positive NPV implies that the investment is profitable; a negative NPV implies that the investment is loss-making (and therefore should be avoided). An "annual equivalent" to the NPV can be calculated which essentially takes the total NPV and, using the period of the investment, calculates an annual amount to help the investor see what their equivalent annual income would be from the investment. If two competing investments cover different time periods then calculating the annual equivalent income from each allows them to be compared directly. It is, however, worth noting that this does not mean that the investment will pay out this income each year and, in fact, in some years an investment may involve only costs and not may not produce an income at all, therefore the cashflow implications should be considered as well as the overall profitability.

Stephen Briggs of Whitehall farm (Case Study 2) provided the data necessary to carry out an NPV calculation for his agroforestry system, an organic apple-arable silvoarable system in Cambridgeshire. The system was initially established in 2009 with a view to preventing wind erosion by providing wind breaks (see Section 3 for more details). The understorey is sown with a wildflower pollen/nectar mix which attracts pollinators and allows the system to receive Higher Level Stewardship (HLS) agri-environment payments which make it more profitable. The trees are apple trees which produce apples for sale mainly through wholesale and which also provide a small amount for juicing. Stephen Briggs provided data on the establishment costs of the agroforestry, the past, present (2014) and anticipated yields of the apples and the income and costs of the apples in 2014. He also provided data on the income and costs associated with the wheat crop planted in the

tree alleys in 2014 (and comparative costs for a non-agroforestry wheat crop, which were in fact identical).

The calculation using the simple NPV calculator yielded a positive NPV, thus it can be seen that the agroforestry system is profitable. The spreadsheet also highlights the reliance on subsidies and agri-environmental payments. In 2014 the income from the single farm payment and HLS is 66% of the total margin.

The NPV calculation can also be used to investigate the impact if the agroforestry system was replaced with a fully arable (all wheat) system or with a system that only produced apples. If it was still eligible for the HLS payment then the wheat-only system would be more profitable than the agroforestry system. In the case that the site is not eligible for any agri-environment payments the NPV would reduce to give a substantial reduction in income. It is likely that the income would lie somewhere between these two extremes. In such a case it is likely that it would be less profitable than the agroforestry but closer in value to it. The NPV calculation can also be used to investigate the impact if the agroforestry system was converted to an apple orchard. This suggests that the apple-only system would be loss-making. It is possible that the apple-only system could be made profitable but it appears that it is unlikely that it would be as profitable as the agroforestry system without major changes to the operation.

FarmSAFE is one of the models developed within a European Commission project called 'Silvoarable Agroforestry for Europe' (SAFE). The aim of the project was to increase the understanding of temperate silvoarable agroforestry relative to conventional arable and forestry systems. The FarmSAFE model was developed to determine and compare the profitability of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems at a farm and a landscape-scale. The existing version of FarmSAFE did not include apple tree systems (the agroforestry systems that were included were timber systems) and so the model needed to be modified to include apple production. The apples were included as a tree by-product and no timber value was taken. The HLS payment was treated as a benefit derived from the trees and so included as a tree grant covering the area of the agroforestry system.

The FarmSAFE model shows that in the total absence of grants, arable production is more profitable than the agroforestry. This highlights the fact that the agroforestry is more profitable due to the HLS environmental payments on the tree strip. However the model also shows that in its current form (i.e. with the HLS payment), the agroforestry system is preferable to the arable. Similarly to the simple NPV calculation results, a scaled-up version of the tree-component of the agroforestry results in an orchard system which is loss-making. However, it was possible using FarmSAFE to calculate break-even apple yields and apple prices which would give zero NPV. These break-even values were within plausible values (especially for the prices) and it is likely that a combination of improved prices and improved yields would be a realistic possibility and could combine to give a positive NPV.

It is worth emphasising that these results are for one agroforestry system in a particular part of the UK which was planted for a very specific purpose. The results suggest that the agroforestry system is the most profitable approach as long as it remains eligible for HLS or similar grants. However, it was planted mainly with the aim of reducing soil erosion rather than with profitability as its main aim. It was noticeable when checking the break-even prices and yields for the scaled-up apple orchard system that the yields and prices currently obtained within the agroforestry system are relatively low. This may be due to the location of the farm (it is not in an apple-growing area of the UK) which

may not provide optimum growing conditions or due to other factors that are specific to the farm. It is therefore difficult to treat these results as representative of UK agroforestry as a whole and care must be taken in interpreting them. However, for this specific farm they suggest that the agroforestry system is profitable and, with the inclusion of an HLS grant, is more profitable than an arable system with no HLS grant. The results also suggest that if the farmer wanted to move over to a fully orchard system then a number of changes would be needed to obtain higher yields and prices as a simple scaling-up of the agroforestry system would not be profitable.

5. An evaluation of management impacts and opportunities

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5.1. Introduction

Within England, silvoarable apple production – the combination of apple trees with arable farming – is an emerging and novel form of temperate agroforestry. These systems are characterized by rows of apple trees or apple trees interspersed with other species, separated by alleys of arable crops allowing access for conventional farm machinery. Being an emerging technology, limited information on the commercial viability of silvoarable apple systems exists within the UK context. As part of the European FP7-funded project ‘Innovative strategies for copper-free low-input and organic farming systems (CO-FREE)’, we have been evaluating agroforestry-based apple production as a potentially sustainable strategy for reducing copper inputs in organic and low-input systems. While there appear to be a number of potential benefits to integrating apple and arable production in terms of reduced disease pressure (Smith et al., 2014), there are likely to be management implications that determine their level of success and commercial viability. This preliminary study aims to identify the main management implications of novel agroforestry-based apple production systems through interviewing both primary and secondary adopters within England.

5.2. Methods

To identify the main management benefits and challenges of integrating apple and arable production systems, a case study approach was used. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants from innovative silvoarable apple systems.

Site description

Four silvoarable apple systems located in East Anglia, the East Midlands and the South West of England were selected as case study sites (Figure 5.1). The dominant farming system within East Anglia is arable production due to deep fertile soils and gently sloping land allowing for the use of large-scale agricultural machinery. Farming in the East Midlands is more diverse due to a broad range of soil types and varied topography, with arable and horticultural production dominant in the east and livestock farming more common in the west. Within the South West of England the dominant farming systems are typically dairy and horticultural production.

Figure 5.1. Location of the four case study sites. East Anglia: Case study 1 & 4; East Midlands: Case study 2; South West: Case study 3.

Case study 1

Case study 1 is a tenanted 104ha organic arable farm located in Cambridgeshire, East Anglia with a 52.6 ha commercial silvoarable apple system. The system was six years old and consisted of rows of apple trees with 24m-wide alleys of combinable crops such as wheat and barley. A total of 4500 apple trees were planted covering 4.84ha; the 13 varieties (9 commercial and 4 traditional) were selected to produce apples for juicing and eating. Apples trees within the rows were spaced every 3m with a planting density of approximately 82 trees per ha. In the 3m-wide strips under the trees, a Higher Level Stewardship (HLS) nectar-rich seed mixture had been sown to encourage pollinators.

Case study 2

Case study 2 was a 260ha conventional arable farm near Nottingham in the East Midlands with a 6ha silvoarable system established less than a year ago. The system consisted of rows of fruit trees (apples, pear, cherry, quince, and nut trees) with 24m-wide alleys in which rape, wheat, spring barley, and beans were cultivated. A total of 450 trees were planted with a 3-metre spacing between each tree. A HLS nectar-rich seed mixture had been established under the trees. The farm was managed under the Linking Environment And Farming program (LEAF).

Case study 3

Case study 3 was a 170ha family-run mixed organic farm located near Exeter in the South West of England. The main farm enterprise was an organic vegetable box scheme. The farm had two silvoarable systems; a 0.4ha system established 12 years ago consisting of rows of apple trees with 12m-wide alleys and a 3.2ha system established 2 years ago containing rows of apple trees with a few plum and pear trees using 28m-wide alleys. Crops grown within the alleys included vegetables, salad, herbs, fruit and cereals such as wheat, barley and oats. Chickens and sheep were also included within the rotation.

Case study 4

Case study 4 was a 22.5ha organic silvoarable research site established in 1994 located in Suffolk, East Anglia. This case study is unusual compared to the three other case studies, being a small-scale experimental farm designed primarily for agroforestry research rather than commercial production. The farm had four silvoarable systems; hazel coppice, willow coppice, a fruit and nut tree system and a mixed hardwood and fruit tree system. The system of interest was a 21-year-old mixed hardwood and fruit tree system covering 2ha. Tree rows consisted of a diverse mix of 21 varieties of apple trees interspersed with 7 timber species (small-leaved lime, hornbeam, wild cherry, Italian alder, ash, oak, sycamore) separated by 12m-wide alleys where fertility-building leys, cereals, potatoes and field vegetables are grown on a six-stage rotation. The margin beneath the tree rows was initially established as a legume ley and had since been left to revert to grass cover.

Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants from each case study (see section 5.2.1). Interviewing methods followed those outlined by Pretty et al. (1995), involved both face-to-face and telephone interviews, and took between 30 and 120 minutes. All interviews were recorded and supported by notes.

An interview guide was used to focus interviews acting as a memory aide to the interviewer (Appendix). Questions covered three main themes: (i) motives for establishing silvoarable agroforestry, (ii) observed benefits and challenges in regards to the main management activities of both arable and apple production, and (iii) the future adoption of silvoarable agroforestry within the UK. All interviews were transcribed and interview notes added to the transcripts.

Content analysis was used to identify dominant topics and concepts, coding the interviews thematically using the software QDA Miner 4 (Provalis Research, 2015). Further analytical steps followed those outlined by Hennink et al. (2010) and included development of thick descriptions for each topic to explore the context and meaning of each issue, cross-case comparisons to highlight patterns across interviews, grouping codes into meaningful categories and exploring the relationships between these categories.

Interview participants

Case study 1: Both tenant farmers (a married couple) from Case study 1 were interviewed individually and face-to-face. Farmer 1 was predominantly involved in the management of the apple trees and understory within the system. Farmer 2, although involved in the general management of the trees, was predominantly responsible for arable crop management.

Case study 2: Farmer 3 was the farm director for Case study 2 and was interviewed over the phone.

Case study 3: Farmer 4 was the second generation of their family to own and run Case study 3 and was interviewed over the phone.

Case study 4: Farmer 5 was the owner and director of Case study 4 and had long been involved in both agroforestry and crop research. Farmer 5 was interviewed face-to-face and accompanied by their spouse. Two local agricultural contractors employed by Farmer 5 to undertake arable management were interviewed together and face-to-face.

5.3. Results

The following section outlines the main findings in terms of farmer objectives, management benefits and challenges, and key factors determining the success and adoption of silvoarable apple systems.

Farmer objectives

Three out of the four case study systems were thought to have been successful in meeting the main objectives behind their implementation, with product diversification, increased biodiversity, reduced soil erosion, provision of shelter and extension of cropping season all being reported. Due to the young age of their system, Farmer 4 (Case study 3) was unable to report whether or not their system had been successful in meeting their objectives.

The most commonly held objective was economic diversification. Perceived benefits of diversification included enhanced biodiversity, reduced economic risk, and resilience to climate change. The second most common objective was improved biodiversity, with interviewees citing habitat creation and improved pest-predator balances as a desired consequence. Individually held motives for implementing silvoarable agroforestry varied with farm location and business type and included soil protection and extended cropping season.

Management benefits

Shelter and biodiversity

One of the main benefits of agroforestry identified by farmers was the provision of shelter. Farmers reported reduced lodging of arable crops, ability to grow early vegetables and reduced soil erosion by wind. All interviewees suggested agroforestry was also beneficial to local wildlife reporting increases in small mammals, farmland birds and increased habitat for beneficial insects.

Pests and disease

The influence of agroforestry on pests and disease was ambiguous, with most farmers unable to comment due to a lack of formal monitoring and absence of an orchard system for comparison. One farmer did however report reductions in pests and disease within their system.

Labour and employment opportunities

The management of apple trees was thought labour intensive, although increases in labour requirements were not considered to be an issue, with most management activities involving apple trees, such as planting, pruning and harvesting, occurring during quieter times of the farming calendar. Integrating apples into the farming system was thought by one farmer to improve rural employment opportunities.

Marketing

Farmers were divided as to whether a certification label is needed for agroforestry produce. However, three out of the four case studies either promoted that their produce was agroforestry grown or were interesting in doing so.

Agricultural equipment

Farmers purchased little in the way of additional equipment for their silvoarable systems. For example, the only additional equipment acquired in Case study 1 was a ride-on mower and storage bins for harvesting the apples. None of the farms used hail nets, trellises, frost protection or irrigation for their apple trees.

Soil health

Although none of the farmers reported they had observed improved soil fertility, two farmers speculated that the tree roots and leaf litter incorporated into the soil during cultivation might be increasing soil organic matter. In addition, none of the farmers believed their reported issues with drainage or water logging to have been influenced by the use of agroforestry.

Management challenges

Experience and knowledge

Being predominantly arable farmers, most had little experience of managing trees before establishing their agroforestry system. All farmers identified a lack of knowledge in terms of both technical design and operation of silvoarable systems as a major challenge during system establishment.

Weed management

Weed management was identified as one of the main management impacts associated with silvoarable systems. There was a general consensus that effective management of the understory is required to ensure tree rows do not become a reservoir for arable weeds. Management of weeds within tree rows included mulching during tree establishment, the use of competitive wildflower mixes, and timely mowing or scything. Most interviewees reported slight increases in weeds such as thistle and couch grass along the edge of tree rows, although two farmers reported the weed burden within the rest of the system to be similar to what most organic arable farmers experience. While less of a concern for organic producers, issues with restricted access for the application of agrichemicals such as herbicides, were also raised.

Pests

A number of trade-offs were identified in regards to pests. Although one farmer reported increased biodiversity they also recognised not all increases had been positive, highlighting an increase in deer presence. Similarly, another farmer reported that although the trees provided shelter for early vegetables, they also provided cover for rabbits and had observed increased rabbit damage as a consequence.

Storage

Although none of the farmers observed difference in grain quality, one farmer explained they had an issue with this year's grain containing clover weevils. Although harmless to the grain itself, the commercial grain store was reluctant to take their grain. Apple storage also presented a challenge to three out of the four farmers due to product perishability and limited on-farm storage facilities.

Tree-crop competition

No indication of tree-crop competition, such as depressed cereal yields, was observed in Case study 1, 2, or 3. This was believed to be due to the young age of the trees. Competition was reported in Case study 4 with variable and depressed yields observed close to the tree rows and near to specific tree species. Whether this resulted in a net yield decrease was unknown. Management activities undertaken within all of the systems to avoid competition included pruning of tree canopies and tree roots.

Wind damage and pollination

Despite the benefits provided by the trees in terms of shelter, wind damage to the trees themselves and reduced pollination were noted as management challenges in Case study 1. Farmer 1 also raised concerns that the root pruning, undertaken to encourage fruiting in fertile soil, may have reduced the trees' resilience against windthrow as they matured.

Security

Within one case study an estimated four tonnes of apples was stolen out of the field overnight. They believed trees provided cover for intruders and regretted locating their system far away from the farmhouse.

Grants and subsidies

All farmers interviewed had received some level of grant funding for the establishment of their silvoarable systems. Although considered helpful, some of the grants received were believed to be limited (i.e. only covered cost of mulch) or dictated system design to some degree (i.e. tree density). Similarly, mowing of HLS wildflower strips in Case study 1 was restricted to certain times by their HLS agreement. To what extent these conditions impacted management was not expressed.

Factors determining success

System design

All interviewees stressed the importance of designing silvoarable systems in terms of both access and desynchronizing management activities. Consideration of the scale of production, size of agricultural machinery, and timing of apple harvest were identified as key design aspects for successful management.

Adaptive management

Precision in system layout and consideration of the size of equipment to be used within the system were found to influence the efficiency of certain management activities. However, both farmers and contractors were found to have adapted management activities to minimise the resulting inefficiencies in field operations.

Factors determining adoption

Knowledge transfer

In regards to adoption, all farmers stressed the importance of knowledge transfer between farmers already managing silvoarable systems and those interested in implementing them. Farmer-led adoption was evident with two of the case study systems having been inspired by an earlier adopter.

Subsidies and grants

A lack of supporting subsidies and conversion grants within the UK for agroforestry was recognised by all of the farmers as a major barrier to system adoption. Despite this, one farmer believed there to be increasing interest in silvoarable systems due to recognition of the benefits such as product diversification and improved utilisation of agricultural land.

Return on investment

Two farmers believed the establishment cost and long-term return on investment for agroforestry systems was prohibitive.

Tenancy

Farm tenancy was raised by three of the farmers as an issue for agroforestry adoption due to the long lifespan of trees in comparison to tenancy agreements. In Case study 1 tenancy also determined the use of apple trees based on their relatively quick return. Longer-lived trees, such as those for timber, were considered unsuitable, as return on investment would rely on their tenancy being renewed.

5.4. Discussion

Three key questions for discussion stem from the results of this study: what are the potential management trade-offs? How can negative management impacts be mitigated? And thirdly, what would be needed for the wider adoption of silvoarable apple systems within England?

Potential trade-offs

Interviews identified a number of direct trade-offs as a result of implementing agroforestry. For example, shelter was recognized as one of the main benefits of silvoarable production with farmers reporting reduced lodging of crops, reduced wind erosion of soil, and an extended cropping season. However, increased tree cover also led to increases in animal pests and issues with security.

All interviewees suggested agroforestry was beneficial to local wildlife, reporting increases in small mammals, farmland birds and increased habitat for beneficial insects. Nevertheless, two farmers recognized not all increases had been positive, highlighting an increase in deer and rabbits. Similar mixed effects on pest control within silvoarable systems are reported in the literature. For example, while silvoarable agroforestry may benefit the control of some arthropod pests, the vegetative cover provided by tree rows has been found to act as a refuge for slugs (Burgess, 1999; Griffiths et al, 1998; Peng et al, 1993).

With the inclusion of trees on agricultural land, additional management complexities are likely to occur. Although wide and straight cropping alleys allow access for large-scale farm machinery, farmers reported tree rows restricted cultivations to one direction, introducing the risk of creating unlevel ground when ploughing and harrowing. One farmer reported a beneficial effect on the control of plant pathogens when apple trees are randomly interspersed with other tree species; a claim supported by Smith et al. (2014). However, they also recognized this irregular arrangement of apple trees was likely to be unsuitable for commercial production due to harvesting complexity and inefficiencies.

In addition to increased management complexity, silvoarable agroforestry may also introduce marketing complexities. Product diversification was the most common objective among farmers for implementing agroforestry. Although producing a range of products was believed to reduce economic risk, one interviewee noted farmers implementing agroforestry are likely to be producing additional products they are unused to growing, and finding suitable markets may therefore be challenging. This may suggest concerns of over-diversification, referring to the situation in which a farm diversifies beyond its optimal limit. Diversified farms are often small and have limited resources to expand into new markets; further diversification may therefore reduce resource availability for 'old activities' and spread a farmer's resources too thinly (Haines & Davies, 1987).

Despite these trade-offs, farmers generally spoke positively about their systems, believing them to be successful in meeting their objectives. This would suggest, in view of the potential benefits provided by silvoarable apple systems, farmers considered the resulting trade-offs to be acceptable.

Mitigating negative impacts

System design

When asked to identify the greatest negative attribute of silvoarable systems, Northern European farmers interviewed by Graves et al. (2009) tended to highlight the general complexity of work and difficulties with mechanization. Furthermore, Umpley and Copas (2002) identify restricted access of mechanical equipment as a major limitation to intercropping within orchards. Having used relatively wide cropping alleys, none of the interviewees reported machinery access to be an issue *per se*, but reported management inefficiencies due to poor pairing of alley width with farm equipment and imprecision in system layout.

Farmer 2 explained that harvesting arable crops was less efficient within their agroforestry system compared to the rest of the farm. This was due to their alleys being 24m wide and the combine harvester being approximately 7m in width. Even though the alleys were more than wide enough to allow machinery access, 24 is not a multiple of 7 resulting in a loss of capacity where the last pass within each alley was over an area already partly harvested. Likewise, Farmer 4 used a six-bed irrigation system despite their cropping alleys being 4-beds wide, resulting in the irrigation system spraying un-cropped areas. In order to mitigate these inefficiencies careful consideration of the size of equipment to be used and appropriate alley width is required during system design. Nevertheless, with the use of multiple pieces of equipment in arable production systems, compromises are inevitable. For example, although Farmer 2 observed reduced efficiency in harvesting, there was no loss of efficiency during cultivation as all of their cultivation equipment was 3m, 6m and 12m in width, of all of which 24 is a multiple.

Accuracy of system layout was also identified as a key consideration for mitigating inefficiency in field operations. Agricultural contractors employed by Farmer 5 reported that, in certain areas of the system, the equipment used did not fit exactly the width of the alleys, leading to inefficiencies in field operations. This was believed to be due to inaccuracies in system layout. Given the opportunity to establish the system again, Farmer 5 said they “would have been much more precise in measuring up the layout so that the alleys would have exactly parallel sides - laser sharp”. Accurate system layout could have easily been achieved with use of a Global Positioning System (GPS) for tree row and tree planting measurements, as done by Farmer 3.

Although irrigation is uncommon within UK apple orchards (Durrant & Durrant, 2009) and none of the farmers interviewed irrigated their apple trees, one farmer suggested irrigation would result in changes in design. To protect the irrigation piping they suggested bringing the ends of the tree rows out of cultivation. This would, however, result in a potential loss of cropping area.

Desynchronization of management activities

Another design consideration is the desynchronization of management activities. For example, reducing overlap of management activities through use of late fruiting varieties and winter pruning, improves access and results in better distribution of labour throughout the year.

The choice of late maturing apple varieties was considered by one farmer to be “crucial”, stating that varieties fruiting in late August were “no good” due to arable crops being present within the alleys and restricting access to harvest the apples. Varieties maturing in late September/October

were therefore used in Case study 1 on the premise that the arable crops would be harvested by late September, and labour would be more readily available for harvesting the apples.

Increased labour requirement was not considered to be an issue due to management activities such as planting, pruning, and harvesting occurring during quieter times of the farming calendar. Labour requirements did however, vary with system design. For example, it is assumed less labour is required for mowing when an understory had been left to revert to grass compared to when a wildflower mix had been used. Equally, it is assumed more labour is required if an understory is cut using a scythe rather than a ride-on mower. Labour availability may therefore influence choice of understory used and its management.

Adaptive management

Both farmers and contractors were found to have adapted management activities to minimise inefficiencies in field operations and to overcome unforeseen management challenges. In Case study 4, a narrow strip of soil was often left to cultivate when agricultural machinery did not fit the alleys exactly. Not being able to drive on the freshly cultivated soil due to the machine getting “bunged up”, contractors cultivated the sides of the alley first, leaving the central strip uncultivated, and took their coffee break while the soil dried out.

As previously mentioned, the formal layout of silvoarable systems restricts movement of agricultural machinery perpendicular to the tree rows. Not being able to cultivate across the cropping alleys was believed to increase the risk of the ground becoming uneven. Farmers therefore tended to use a power harrow, allowing soil to be evenly distributed across the alleys due to its circular motion. This ability to adapt and innovate was also observed in response to management challenges such as low pollination and wind damage to apple trees, which were addressed through the planting of a shelterbelt, a change in formative pruning, and the introduction of beehives. This would suggest an adaptive and flexible management approach is an important attribute for the successful management of silvoarable systems.

Effective weed management

Weed management is one of the main challenges in organic arable farming (Briggs, 2008) and was identified by farmers as one of the main management impacts associated with silvoarable systems. Within conventional orchards an easy to manage, low vigour sward would be established under the trees, whereas in a silvoarable system only a strip is left uncultivated under the tree rows (Durrant and Durrant, 2009). In their review of recent developments in cider orcharding, Durrant and Durrant (2009) argue the management of this strip may be difficult and ultimately lead to weed problems, and that the use of black plastic or organic mulches such as wood chip may harbour damaging pests.

There was a general consensus among interviewees that effective management of the understory is required to ensure tree rows do not become a reservoir for arable weeds. Management of weeds within tree rows included mulching during tree establishment, the use of competitive wildflower mixes, and timely mowing or scything before weeds set seed. Most interviewees reported slight increases in weeds such as thistle and couch grass along the edge of tree rows, although two farmers reported weed burden within the rest of the system to be similar to what most organic arable farmers experience.

One farmer, worried that the tree margins would become a reservoir for arable weeds, mowed regularly during establishment. In hindsight, they believed this level of management was unnecessary and that, if left undisturbed, the composition of the understory would have naturally transitioned to tussocky grasses such as cocksfoot (*Dactylis glomerata*), able to out-compete arable weeds. The contractors, on the other hand, believed regular mowing during the early years of system establishment had been crucial in achieving this compositional change, and even now they stop weeds spreading by occasionally mowing areas where issues with bramble, docks or thistles occur. They reported that in another field they had reduced the intensity of mowing much earlier and believed issues with thistles had persisted longer because of this. This suggests that although tree margins may well transition if left unmanaged, regular mowing during establishment may speed up the transition from arable weeds to grasses.

In Case study 1, two different wildflower mixes were sown under the trees. One of the mixes was believed to be better than the other at suppressing weeds due to a higher density of knapweed (*Centaurea nigra*) and Red Campion (*Silene dioica*); tussocky species able to outcompete arable weeds. This would suggest using a well-suited wildflower seed mixture as an understory may help reduce weeds through competition.

The farmers used a number of different mulch materials with varying success. Although the use of MyPex® mats initially worked well in Case study 1, the mats were now considered a “liability” as they got caught in the ride-on mower when cutting the understory. Based on the advice of a local apple tree supplier, straw mulch was used in Case study 4 encouraging “vast amounts of couch grass”. Despite the importance of using mulch to suppress weed growth during tree establishment being recognized, which mulches are best suited to these systems is unclear.

Although less of a concern for organic producers, issues with restricted access for the application of agrichemicals such as herbicides, were also raised. Although herbicides may be used for weed control both under the trees and within the alleys, it may be difficult to acquire selective herbicides for tree and crop components with no negative impact to the other (Braun et al, 2004). The use of spray guards such as those used in forest establishment could be used to mitigate spray drift onto crops when spraying young trees. Reducing spray drift from arable applications is likely to be more challenging.

Knowledge and advice

Lack of knowledge in terms of both technical design and operation of agroforestry-based apple systems was identified as a major challenge to both system establishment and wider system adoption. Being primarily arable farmers with little knowledge of tree management, two interviewees had sought advice on apple tree varieties and establishment. Although the advice was likely given with good intention, Farmer 5 was recommended to use straw as mulch for the apple trees, which later resulted in acute weed issues. This may have been a result of the adviser themselves being inexperienced with silvoarable systems. One farmer explained that although advice on tree planting is now widely available to farmers through organizations such as the Woodland Trust, farmers still require continued support on tree-based management.

Farmers also experienced unforeseen consequences resulting from management decisions made during system establishment. For example, the use of tree shelters rather than tree guards resulted

in poor tree form for Farmer 5, and use of longer tree supports in Case study 1 could have prevented young trees being damaged by perching birds. Such knowledge gained through experience could be very useful to those wishing to establish silvoarable systems in the future. Knowledge transfer not only between farmers and advisers, but between farmers already managing silvoarable systems and those interested in implementing them, will help to improve future design and management of silvoarable apple systems.

Managing competition

Management of both positive and negative tree-crop interactions is considered to be the biophysical determinant of successful agroforestry systems (Sanchez, 1995). Many tree-crop interactions, especially those belowground, are however difficult to measure. The interactions noted by farmers were therefore largely based on informal observation.

No indication of tree-crop competition, such as depressed cereal yields, was observed in Case studies 1, 2, or 3. This was believed to be due to the young age of the trees. Competition was reported in Case study 4 with variable yields observed close to the tree rows. Although Farmer 5 had observed strong competition for water near to ash trees, they speculated crop yields might be higher nearer Italian alder due to nitrogen fixation. Whether such interactions resulted in a net yield increase or decrease was unknown.

Farmer 5 also suggested the wide alleys used in large-scale silvoarable systems, despite being easier to manage with larger machinery, might be missing out on beneficial tree-crop interactions, especially when smaller trees are used. Although beneficial interactions such as shelter are reduced through use of wider alleys, it may be true that negative interactions such as competition for nutrients and water are reduced.

Management activities undertaken to avoid competition included pruning of both tree canopies and tree roots. In Case study 1 they purposely sub-soiled deeply close to the tree rows. Being on very fertile soils, this was primarily to encourage the trees to fruit rather than focus their resources on horizontal root growth. In Case study 4 the objective was to reduce competition and the interference of roots when cultivating. Farmer 1 raised concerns that root pruning may reduce the trees' windblow resistance. Although root pruning was considered to be a necessity, they suggested stronger tree supports might be a solution.

An interesting proposal to mitigate tree-crop competition, raised by Farmer 5, was the use of more suitable crops for silvoarable agroforestry. Having been a leading researcher in the development of a diverse and evolving wheat population (Döring et al, 2011), Farmer 5 believed one advantage of the population approach is being able to select plants for their ability to grow in certain conditions. They suggested it would be possible to "build a population" from selected plants that grow well at the edge of the alleys and drill this subset along the edge of the tree rows.

In their review of recent developments in cider orcharding, Durrant and Durrant (2009) suggest cultivation for the management of crops may reduce water content and damage soil structure. Interviewees however reported neither water stress nor damage to soil structure.

Location and aspect

Management challenges are likely to vary with system location and biophysical context; such factors therefore need to be considered when designing silvoarable systems. Case study 1, for example, was established within a very flat and exposed landscape. Despite the benefits provided by the apple trees in terms of shelter to crops, wind damage to the trees was noted as a management challenge. Had they planted a windbreak to protect vulnerable trees before establishing the silvoarable system, the extent of wind damage could have been lessened.

Wider system adoption

One of the primary challenges in developing an alternative farming system is for it to be adopted and maintained by farmers (Pannell, 1999). For farmers to adopt a new farming practice they must be aware of the innovation, acknowledge its feasibility, and perceive that the innovation promotes their objectives (Pannell, 1999). Farmer-led adoption was evident, with two of the case studies having been inspired by an earlier adopter; this suggests farmers perceived silvoarable apple systems to be viable and implies scope for wider farmer uptake within England.

Although all farmers stressed the importance of farmer-to-farmer knowledge transfer for the adoption of silvoarable agroforestry, one farmer believed organisations such as the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, Natural England and Forestry Commission had little knowledge of the subject and therefore tended to dismiss it. It was also recognised that other agricultural stakeholders such as commercial grain stores may have little awareness of agroforestry practices, highlighting the importance of not only farmer-to-farmer knowledge transfer but raising awareness of these systems more widely.

Across Europe, agroforestry frequently falls between forestry and agriculture and therefore often qualifies for neither set of subsidy payments (Eichhorn et al, 2006). A shortfall of supporting subsidies and conversion grants within the UK for silvoarable systems was recognised by all of the farmers as a major barrier for adoption. Changes to policy and increased support are therefore likely to be needed. Additionally, all of the farmers had received some level of grant funding for system establishment. Although some of grants were limited, one farmer believed system establishment might not have been possible without a planting grant, highlighting the importance of their continued availability.

Study limitations

Due to time constraints no follow-up interviews were conducted. Having had further opportunities for interviewing, management implications could have been explored in more detail. Two of the interviews were conducted over the phone; resulting in shorter interviews and limiting the depth. Face-to-face interviews would have been preferable.

Due to limited willingness to participate, only two agricultural contractors from one case study were interviewed. Interviews with system managers for the four systems could have provided supplementary insight not available from primary and secondary adopters. The management of silvoarable systems in general is likely similar to arable/apple systems; widening the scope of the interviews to non-apple silvoarable farmers may therefore provide useful insights into potential management implications.

Evaluation of the economic viability was not reported due to most case studies not having reached production maturity, and Case 2 only just having been established. Farmer 3 was therefore unable to comment on many of the management implications of silvoarable apple agroforestry. Whether the systems will be profitable once economic productivity is reached is unknown.

5.5. Conclusion

This preliminary study provides insight into the potential benefits and management challenges associated with novel silvoarable apple systems. Although farmers reported a number of management issues and unforeseen challenges in the design, establishment and on-going operation of their systems, they also spoke of substantial benefits in terms of product diversification, increased biodiversity, reduced soil erosion, and the provision of shelter. Four out of the five farmers interviewed believed their systems to have been successful in meeting their objectives, suggesting such benefits may well outweigh any management inconveniences. Nevertheless, a number of approaches to mitigating the management impacts of integrating apple and cereal production were identified. These included appropriate system design, de-synchronization of management activities, effective management of tree-crop competition and weeds, and the ability of farmers and contractors to adapt management practices.

Evidence of farmer-led adoption suggests farmers perceive silvoarable apple systems to be viable, implying scope for wider uptake within England. Through their trial and error, these farmers and contractors have gained significant knowledge on the design and management of these systems. Such knowledge will be invaluable to those establishing future silvoarable apple systems and silvoarable agroforestry more broadly. However this study also identified a number of substantial knowledge gaps. This calls for, not only further documentation of existing systems, but further trials on their establishment, operation and commercial performance. As recognized by all five of the farmers interviewed, in addition to continued research, favourable policy changes and conversion grants will be required for wider adoption of agroforestry-based apple production within the UK.

6. Evaluation of novel agroforestry-based apple production systems

This research aimed to evaluate an apple/arable agroforestry approach as a sustainable strategy for reducing copper inputs in organic and low input systems using two case studies; Wakelyns Agroforestry, Suffolk, UK (Section 2) and Whitehall Farm, Cambridgeshire, UK (Section 3).

Research focused on five elements that are likely to be impacted by an agroforestry systems approach to no-copper use:

- (i) Yield and quality of apples (Sections 2 and 3)
- (ii) Emergence of primary and secondary pests and diseases (Sections 2 and 3),
- (iii) Impact on ecosystem services and functionality (Sections 2 and 3),
- (iv) The economics of agroforestry-based apple production (Section 4),
- (v) Impact on management activities (Section 5).

6.1. Discussion

Yields at Wakelyns in 2012 and 2013 were comparable with standard figures when scaled up from 2.5% land area under apple production to 100% apples, and even at just 2.5% cover, appeared to out-perform the organic orchard used for comparison. With so few apple trees, this would probably not be acceptable for large scale apple producers who rely on economies of scale. However, this approach could work well in a diverse, potentially small-scale system such as a market garden, where apples could contribute to direct marketing channels such as vegetable box schemes or farm shops. Having such a wide range of varieties within the system means that harvesting would occur over a longer period. This requires careful planning and may be a challenge for selling to wholesalers if only small amounts are ready at any one time. New approaches to marketing could address this problem, for example, creating mixed bags of varieties, categorizing by taste, e.g. 'sweet' apple bag, or 'sharp' apple bag; or by making more of a feature of the varieties if going into vegetable box schemes e.g. 'apple of the week'.

In the more commercial system at Whitehall Farm, tree rows account for 10% land area with 85 trees/ha; scaling up to 100% apples, yields compared well with standard yields. Considering that the apple trees at Whitehall were planted only in 2009 and so the system is still establishing and developing, the apple yields look promising, with some varieties performing much better than others.

Neither case study systems spray to control for scab or other diseases or pests, and scab was detected in both systems during the years of study. At Wakelyns, scab levels were several times lower than in the nearby organic orchard in both 2012 and 2013. Although no firm general conclusion can be drawn from this case study, it appears as if there may be indications of a potential positive impact on reducing scab levels within the agroforestry. This could be due to the very low densities and high diversity of apple tree varieties. Also, that while some varieties may fail to set fruit or have high levels of scab, the high diversity of apple varieties within the agroforestry means that other varieties will compensate and so buffer against extreme losses of yields. However, further research will be required to confirm this theory.

Scab was recorded in the apples at Whitehall Farm at quite high levels, particularly in 2014, and in one variety (Falstaff) in 2015, although the resistant variety Red Windsor maintained its resistance. However, the apple varieties studied seemed to perform poorly, while other varieties in the system yielded well and had fewer pests and diseases, which demonstrates the value of planting a wide range of varieties. The varieties were planted in blocks, which is likely to have facilitated the spread of pests and diseases, despite the crop alleys in between tree rows. It may therefore be better to mix varieties within the rows and fields, although this then becomes a challenge to manage and harvest efficiently.

In both case study systems, the impacts of secondary pests and diseases varied between the agroforestry systems and the orchards, This supports previous research on agroforestry systems that while some pests are reduced in agroforestry systems, other pest groups may be observed in higher numbers, and shifts in relative importance of pest groups may present novel management problems and influence crop choice (Griffiths et al., 1998).

This study provided useful insight into the potential benefits and management challenges associated with novel silvoarable apple systems. Although farmers reported a number of management issues and unforeseen challenges in the design, establishment and on-going operation of their systems, they also spoke of substantial benefits in terms of product diversification, increased biodiversity, reduced soil erosion, and the provision of shelter, with most believing that their systems had been successful in meeting their objectives, suggesting such benefits may well outweigh any management inconveniences. Nevertheless, a number of approaches to mitigating the management impacts of integrating apple and cereal production were identified. These included appropriate system design, de-synchronization of management activities, effective management of tree-crop competition and weeds, and the ability of farmers and contractors to adapt management practices.

Evidence of farmer-led adoption suggests farmers perceive silvoarable apple systems to be viable, implying scope for wider uptake within England. However the interviews also identified a number of substantial knowledge gaps. This calls for not only further documentation of existing systems but further trials on their establishment, operation and commercial performance. As recognized by all five of the farmers interviewed, in addition to continued research, favourable policy changes and conversion grants will be required for wider adoption of agroforestry-based apple production within the UK.

6.2. Potential synergies and tensions

Combining apple production with arable production aims to maximize synergies between the different components while minimizing negative interactions. Potential synergies within the two case-study systems, including those identified by the farmers, include Increased biodiversity resulting in increases in natural enemies; high diversity of apple varieties reducing diseases and spreading risk from crop failure; and shelter from trees reducing wind impacts on arable and vegetable crops. However, trade-offs were also identified. For example, encouraging apple pollinators in an arable system using floral mixtures as at Whitehall Farm may also lead to increases in certain pests e.g. capsids. And while there may be benefits of increasing varietal diversity, reducing tree densities and encouraging mixed plantings of varieties in terms of reducing the spread of disease, this would have implications for efficient harvesting, management and marketing.

6.3. Conclusion

The two case study systems provided contrasting approaches to agroforestry-based apple production in terms of scale and design. The low density, high diversity approach at Wakelyns Agroforestry seemed to have benefits in terms of reducing disease levels, and could work well in a diverse, potentially small-scale system such as a market garden, where apples could contribute to direct marketing channels such as vegetable box schemes or farm shops. The commercial silvoarable system at Whitehall Farm showed that an agroforestry approach per se is not successful at reducing scab levels. However, if combined with careful selection of resistant varieties and, if possible, mixed planting of varieties, the other benefits that agroforestry brings, particularly to arable systems, may make this approach attractive to arable farmers looking to diversify their enterprises or protect their farms against environmental problems.

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8. Appendix

CO-FREE Interview Guide

System design and layout

Please could you describe the system's layout and design?

Planting density, alley width, access, rootstocks, crop varieties, understory, altered rotations

Are there any benefits?

Tree-crop interactions, diversity, biodiversity

Are there any challenges?

Access, density, pollination, poor choice of varieties

System establishment

Why did you establish the system?

Diversity, profit, biodiversity, funding, site visits to other systems

How did you establish the system?

Land preparation, mulch, sequence, machinery used, and process (progressive or sudden)

Have you observed any benefits?

Have you observed any challenges?

Poor establishment, cost, labour, time

Soil management

What soil management do you undertake for the arable crops?

Timing, frequency, depth, machinery, other management, claying, liming

What soil management do you undertake for the trees?

Timing, frequency, depth, machinery, other management, claying, liming

Have you observed any benefits?

Improved structure, less erosion

Have you observed any challenges?

Conflicting regimes, access, increased traffic, compaction, pH, erosion, damage to roots, labour

Fertility management

How do you manage fertility for the arable crops?

Fertilizer form, amount, timing, application method, leys and legumes

How do you manage fertility for the trees?

Fertilizer form, amount, timing, application method, leys and legumes

Have you observed any benefits?

Increased fertility, changes in soil chemistry and microbiological activity, less leaching, decreased labour

Have you observed any challenges?

Differing requirements, changes in soil chemistry and microbiological activity, leaching, labour

Crop establishment

How are the arable crops established?

Direct drilling, broadcasted, undersown, seed rate, drilling depth, sowing times

Have you observed any benefits?

Decreased labour, better establishment

Have you observed any challenges?

Competition, light, water, nutrients, different sowing time and seed rates used, labour

Water management

Do you manage water within the system?

Irrigation, drainage, ditches, mole plough, pipe drains, rain gun, sprinkler, underground pipe

Have you observed any benefits?

Increased soil moisture, less runoff, less labour

Have you observed any challenges?

Tree roots, reduced moisture from cultivations, water logging, runoff, labour

Weed management

Do you manage weeds within the arable cropping area?

Rotations, cultivations, frequency and number of operations, fallowing, false beds, inter row weeding, machinery

Have you observed any benefits?

Reduced weed burden

Have you observed any challenges?

Increased weed burden, damage to tree roots

Do you manage weeds under the trees?

Mowing, sward establishment, mulch

Have you observed any benefits?

Reduced weed burden

Have you observed any challenges?

Increased weeds, mowing, mulches, labour

Pest and disease management

Do you manage pests and diseases within the arable cropping area?

Rotations, cultivations, resistant varieties, diversity

Have you observed any benefits?

Decreased pests and diseases

Have you observed any challenges?

Increased pest and disease

Do you manage pests and disease for the trees?

Chemical, mechanical, pruning, cultural, shredding, guards, supports, scarecrows, shooting, fungicides

Have you observed any benefits?

Decreased pests and diseases

Have you observed any challenges?

Increased pest and disease, replacing guards and supports, labour, conflicting regimes

Tree management

How do you manage tree growth?

Pruning, training, timing, frequency, tools, machinery, labour

Have you observed any benefits?

Reduced shading, less resource competition

Have you observed any challenges?

Access, crop damage, labour, cost, time

Harvesting

How do you harvest the arable crops?

Machinery, timing, labour

Have you observed any benefits?

Easy access, low labour, jobs, low cost, time, increased yield

Have you observed any challenges?

Access, tree damage, labour availability, cost, time, lodging, cleaning, leaf litter and debris, yield decrease

How do you harvest the apples?

Mechanically, by hand, machines used

Have you observed any benefits?

Labour, jobs, low cost, time, increased yield

Have you observed any challenges?

Access, crop damage, labour availability, cost, time, yield decrease

Storage

How do you store the arable crops?

Barn, silos, on-farm, off-farm, packed, dried

Have you observed any benefits?

Longer storage

Have you observed any challenges?

Distance, pest and disease, cost, labour, spoiling, variability, temperature, humidity and moisture content

How do you store the apples?

Barn, on-farm, off-farm, packed, dried

Have you observed any benefits?

Longer storage

Have you observed any challenges?

Distance, pest and disease, cost, labour, spoiling, variability, moisture, temperature, humidity

Processing

How are the arable crops processed?

Final products, on-farm, off-farm, equipment

Have you observed any benefits?

Have you observed any challenges?

Distance, cost, labour, variability, cleaning

How are the apples processed?

Final products, on-farm, off-farm, equipment

Have you observed any benefits?

Have you observed any challenges?

Distance, cost, labour, variability, cleaning

Marketing

How are the arable crops marketed and sold?

End products, wholesale, restaurant, locally, artisans

Have you observed any benefits?

Niche market, premium, quality, weight, grain density, purity

Have you observed any challenges?

No market, under and over supply, produce quality

How are the apples marketed and sold?

End products, wholesale, restaurant, locally, artisans

Have you observed any benefits?

Niche market, premium, and quality

Have you observed any challenges?

No market, under and over supply, produce quality, weight, appearance

System adoption

What do you think the future for such systems will be?

Uptake, adoption, need for subsidies and support

Do or did you receive any grants, subsidies or support the system?

Closing questions

Are there any other key management activities you would like to add?

What changes would you make to the system?

Do you have any other comments you would like to add?